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CENTRE FOR
DEVELOPMENT
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EDUCATION CHALLENGES: QUALITY AND INCLUSION

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In collaboration with

US-INDIA
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INTRODUCTION

India's education sector is indeed in a bad state. There are serious problems with respect to access to education itself, and quality education is simply not available. 89% of kids of primary school-going age of the richest 20 per cent of the population attend school both in the rural and urban areas, while that proportion drops to 79% for kids in the poorest fifth of the population in rural areas and 78% in urban areas. But, attendance drops sharply when it comes to secondary school and becomes worse at the higher secondary level. Also, the difference between the richest and the poorest in enrolment widens sharply from the primary section to the secondary and higher educational levels.

The gulf between the poor and the rich widens as we go up the ladder. Only 6% of young people from the bottom 20 per cent of the population attend educational levels above higher secondary in urban India, while 31% among the richest 20 per cent of the population attend secondary school. The middle class is also substantially disadvantaged when it comes to higher education. The situation is substantially worse in rural India. What happens, therefore is that the richer children have much better opportunities for higher education, essential for getting good jobs in the cities. These are also the children who travel abroad for jobs and for higher education. The poorer children must then work in the informal sector at low wages and remain vulnerable.

Muslims have the highest percentage of illiterates aged beyond seven years at 42.72%, as compared to 36.40% among Hindus, 32.49% among Sikhs, 28.17% among Buddhists and 25.66% among Christians. Jains have the highest percentage of literates above seven years of age among India's religious communities, with Census India 2011 finding 86.73% of them as literate and only 13.57% as illiterate. As per the latest data released on 'education level by the religious community for age seven and above' by the government, other minority communities score over both Hindus and Muslims in literacy levels. As compared to 63.60% of Hindus and 57.28% Muslims in the 'literate' category, the percentage of literates among Christians is 74.34%, among Buddhists 71.83% and among Sikhs 67.51%.

What is indeed sad is that across the country, 29 per cent of children drop out before completing five years of primary school, and 43 per cent before finishing upper primary school. Only 42 per cent get to complete high school.

This ensures that India stands among the top five nations for out-of-school children of primary school age, with 1.4 million children in the age group 6 to 11-year-olds not attending school. What does not help at all is that a number of schools are not equipped to handle the complete population. There is a teacher shortage of 689,000 teachers in primary schools. Just about 53 percent of schools have functional girls' toilets, and 74 per cent have access to drinking water.

Some states have wide gender differences at the secondary levels. For instance, net attendance rates at the secondary level in Gujarat is 63% for boys and 43% for girls. Gujarat is one of India's most industrialised states but shows some strange results on how girls are treated there. The sex ratio in Gujarat came down to 919 in 2011 from 920 in 2001 as against a significant increase of 10 points in the national average during this period. As against the national figure of 943, the overall sex ratio of Gujarat was 919 in 2011. Sex ratio is the number of girls to every 1000 boys in the population. A low sex ratio indicates very high levels of discrimination against the female gender.

Going back to education, the difference between scheduled castes and tribes and other categories widens at higher levels of education. It is particularly large for urban girls belonging to scheduled tribes at the secondary and higher secondary levels. Enrolment of Muslims is lower compared to those of other religions at every level, both for males and females. In urban India, while enrolment for Muslim boys in primary schools is only marginally lower, the proportion at the higher educational levels is substantially lower. Muslim girls enrol in comparable numbers in primary schools, but the drop-out rates at secondary levels are alarming,

Much of this can be attributed to the low levels of expenditure on education. According to the World Bank indicators, government expenditure on education as a percentage of gross domestic product was 3.8% for India in 2012. Compared to other poor countries it is abysmally low. The figure is 6.3% for Vietnam, 4.3% for Mali, 4.7% for Nepal and 5% for Rwanda. As a result, the state is unable to provide education infrastructure to a large number of the poor. It also results in primary schools rarely getting upgraded to secondary levels, forcing a number of our children to stop studying after primary levels as they are not able to travel long distances to continue their education. What is simply inexplicable is the state building primary schools

after the Right to Education Act has been passed. The RTE mandates compulsory education for children in the 6 to 14 age groups. How then can it justify making schools only for the 6 to 10 - year-olds? What the RTE now implies is that there cannot be stand-alone primary schools anywhere, and certainly not in areas where there are no other schools. All primary schools must immediately be converted to secondary schools.

Lastly, there is one rather disturbing feature in this data. While Jains are the most literate groups in the country, it is distressing that the girl child is treated badly. Sikhs and Jains have the worst sex ratio in the country, as per additional census data. According to the 2011 census, there were 828 girls in the age of 0 to 6 years in the Sikh community in comparison to 1,000 boys. Among the Jains, there were 889 girls against 1,000 boys in the age group of 0 to 6 years. The child sex ratio of the total population in the country was 918 girls against 1,000 boys. Education does not seem to help the gender divide among our most educated communities.

With a middle-class population exceeding 300 million, India is the largest market for automobiles, high- value foods, mobile phones etc., ahead of or just behind China. This turnaround has happened as education levels have gone up - nearly 98% of children are enrolled in primary schools now. Another reason is the fall in fertility rates, where now an average Indian family has less than three children compared to five, a couple of decades ago, leading to increased expense on education and healthier child. There is enough debate on this now. Are demographics India's biggest challenge, as argued in the Economist's cover story¹, or do they give India the opportunity for a truly knowledge-based economy it looks for? If India is to seize new opportunities that the new millennium brings², it will have to overhaul its higher education sector. The key to it is to create a large number of skilled people year after year. Nearly 10 million youth will join the workforce every year for at least another decade, and to skill them will take a gigantic effort.

The sobering facts are rather dramatic. Even now, India is far behind all developed and even most developing countries. According to the 2011 census, the literacy rate has reached 74%, which means that even now, 25% of

1 The Economist, May 11, 2013.

2 Scott argues that the challenges facing higher education in the new millennium cannot be understood unless proper account is taken of the phenomenon of globalisation. Scott, P. (2000).

the population remains completely unlettered. At the tertiary level, in terms of our children seeking university education, the Gross Enrolment Ratio is an abysmal 16%, while the world average is over 27%. Only 17 million children have access to university seats. Even now, only about 15% of our children matriculate, and just half the number ever reach college. According to a 2011 India's Planning Commission sponsored study, the deficit in the number of seats in school had reached 60 million. This means that 60 million children in India today don't have a school seat even if they want to attend school. At the university level, this means that if just 30% attend university, at least 36 million more seats need to be created. With a total number of about 900 universities now, India still needs double the number.

India still shows remarkably high inequality in terms of access to education and health facilities³. For India to sustain the growth momentum and achieve greater heights in education and economy sector, it is imperative that it builds institutions that skill the large numbers of youth entering the labour markets every year. A new beginning from early stages of life, redrawn primary education pedagogies, a lesser emphasis on examinations, trained teachers and significantly higher incentives to research are what the education sector for tomorrow needs.

METHODOLOGY

The primary aim of the study was to assess what brings quality to school education. The study looks at what makes certain schools attract and retain students. For the purpose of analysing this, the project was divided into two components.

In the first part, experts in the field of education were consulted. Their perceptions and experiences on various aspects of education were transcribed and analysed qualitatively.

3 The Human Development Report cautions that even now about 1.6 billion people, 30 per cent of the population in the 104 developing and poor countries, live in poor conditions. It also states that income inequality has been going up in many countries of the world. While overall inequality has marginally declined in the last two decades, it is the inequality on health and education that has grown. Sub Saharan Africa for example, shows the highest inequality in terms of access to health and health indicators, while South Asia shows the highest inequality in terms of access to education and educational achievements.

- Farhad Merchant
- Gowri Iswaran
- Jyotsana Brar
- Kiran Bir Sethi
- Meeta W Sengupta
- Pankaj Jain
- Pankaj Tripathi
- Rekha Dey
- Ritesh Singh
- Romana Shaikh
- Sameen Fatima
- Tarun
- Umme Salma

For the second part, the team at CDPP spoke to school administrators, directors and teachers in Hyderabad, covering various boards, curriculums and management. The idea was to look at each school's journey to understand their strengths, weaknesses and challenges. Each of those learnings have been put together in a case study format. The analysis helps us to arrive at what essentially makes a good school.

- Al Falah School
- Azaan International School
- Chowraha Jinsi Govt. Primary School
- Creekside International School
- Focus High School
- Glendale International School
- Hyderabad Public School
- Iqra Mission High School
- Madina Public School
- Mount Mercy School
- Princess Esin Girls' High School

The study has used a combination of primary and secondary data. The data has been analysed qualitatively.

SECTION - 1

WHAT BRINGS QUALITY TO EDUCATION?

This section of the report is based on the inputs received by individuals who have left an indelible footprint in the field of education. These experts have provided insights on various aspects of education that bring quality in the process and outcome. The perceptions and narratives of the following people have been used to define the elements that make up for an effective education system:

- **Farhad Merchant** has 25+ years of versatile experience in the corporate and social sectors, with international exposure, having worked with clients from various countries and sectors/industries. As CEO at Aga Khan Education Service (AKES), India, he drives organisational change and the school improvement agenda. He is responsible for the India portfolio, focused on bringing in best practices and educational excellence across all units to achieve effective student learning outcomes.
- **Gowri Iswaran** is the recipient of the coveted Padmashri Award from the Govt. of India in 2004. She is an innovative educationist with over 30 years of experience in leading schools of India. She has been the Founder Principal of Sanskriti School, New Delhi. She is currently the Vice Chairman of The Global Education and Leadership Foundation. She is also on the Advisory Board of the Shiv Nadar Foundation.
- **Jyotsana Brar** is Member of the CBSE and the Examinations Committee of the Council for the ICSE. Governing Council Member for The Latika Roy Foundation and 'Raphael' Ryder Cheshire Home. Member of the Board and the Academics Committee of the Himjyoti School Dehradun, a residential school for girls from economically weaker families of different districts of Uttarakhand. Recipient of the Pride of Uttarakhand Award, the Indian Public Schools Conference Lifetime Achievement Award and the NDTV-Educomp Lifetime Achievement Award.
- **Kiran Bir Sethi** is an Indian designer, educationist, education reformer, and social entrepreneur. She founded the award-winning Riverside School in Ahmedabad that focuses on empowering children with the I CAN MINDSET – nourished with humane values. She then founded aProCh (an

initiative to make our cities more child friendly) and finally Design for Change which is today the one of the largest movements of change – for and by the children. Today, DFC is in more than 60 countries – and children use the simple design thinking framework to design solutions for some of their greatest challenges.

- **Meeta W. Sengupta** is a Fellow of the Salzburg Global Seminar, and a Fellow of the Royal Society of Arts et al. Meeta has been the founder of the Centre for Education Strategy, a Delhi based think tank that builds bridges between policy and practice for educators, educationists and Institutions. She has been the Senior Advisor, Centre for Civil Society. She has been a member of the FICCI (Federation of Indian Chambers of Commerce and Industry) Skills Development Forum. She is the member Education Expert on the National Council of NISA (National Independent Schools Alliance) that represents over 6000 budget schools.
- **Pankaj Jain** is Founder-Chief Functionary of the Education Support Organisation, which runs Gyan Shala, an NGO that serves the educational needs of several districts across multiple districts in India. Gyan Shala is a unique model that seeks to educate children by focusing primarily on curriculum development, and thus reducing the costs associated with educating children. Jain works extensively with the Gyan Shala model in the slums of Ahmedabad and Bihar.
- **Pankaj Tripathi** is an ex-Civil Servant. After serving with the Government of India for 25years (1993-2018) in different capacities within India and in Indian Diplomatic Missions abroad, including in Islamabad, Central Asia and Frankfurt. He has been working in the social sector since February 2019, as Principal Consultant with the Sarojini Damodaran Foundation (SDF) that supports the education of students from economically disadvantaged families.
- **Rekha Dey** is a sport and development specialist with over 19 years of experience. She has been a Member, Expert Reference Group for the development of a MOOC on sport, development and building peaceful and inclusive societies, an initiative of the Commonwealth Secretariat and the Australian government (2019-20). She has held various positions in the past. She was India Coordinator for the Australian Sports Outreach

Program (ASOP), a ‘Sport for Development’ program of the Government of Australia (2012-15); She was Director at Sports Education Development Australia (2015-18), an Australian training provider in the fitness sector.

- **Ritesh Singh** is the co-founder of Eckovation. Eckovation had ensured the reach of quality education to more than 10 million students and projects of Eckovation won prestigious awards like Prime Minister’s Excellence Award and Commonwealth International Innovation Award. During college, he also started a non-profit organisation, SARAS, to help the masses get access to education technology developed by universities in India and abroad. It was the time spent working with SARAS that urged him to join Avanti, a non-profit organisation that provides low-income high-school students with a world-class science and mathematics education.
- **Romana Shaikh** is a 2009 Teach for India alumnus, Romana served as the Director, Training & Impact team at Teach for India where she led large teams to expand the purpose and scope of educational outcomes. Today, Romana coaches’ schools globally with Kizazi, enabling them to innovate and design learning that is empowering of culture and diversity. Continuing her practice as a facilitator and community builder, she supports various initiatives, including the Thrive collaborative, The Mind Room and because you, a social enterprise for mental health.
- **Syeda Sameen Fatima** did her post-graduation from University of Massachusetts, USA and received her Doctorate in Computer Science & Engineering from Osmania University, Hyderabad. She has 37 years of rich teaching, research and administration experience from OU, UoH, BITS and University of Massachusetts at Amherst in USA.
- **Mohd. Suleman Siddiqui** is Former Vice Chancellor of Osmania University.
- **Kaushiki Sanyal** is Co-founder and CEO, Sunay Advisory
- **Meera Shenoy** is a pioneer in job-linked skilling of rural, tribal and now youth with disabilities. She was Executive Director, EGMM, the first State government skilling mission, then consulted with the World Bank and UNDP, and is now a Change maker. She set up Youth4Jobs 9 years back

which has grown to be the largest organisation in South Asia skilling less educated and educated youth with disabilities and linking them to jobs. Y4J is a one stop shop for 650+ companies has won the highest National and international awards.

- **Tarun** is an IISER Pune alumnus, is a Mathematician by training, who started teaching at 16 and founded Sciensation. tv at 19, to spreading university-level research-based thinking. Tarun is the founder of DeepThought EduTech Ventures, working towards the ambitious goal of scaling the MIT/Harvard/IISERs kind of education to the rest of the world. DeepThought is replacing the paradigm of “experts teach students” with “senior learners teach junior learners”. They emphasise the mindset / processes over content/curriculum.
- **Umme Salma** is the founding Principal of New York Academy, a progressive American school in Hyderabad. She is also an Adjunct Professor at Notre Dame de Namur University in California. Umme is the Founder and Director of EdPodium, a non-profit organisation in California. EdPodium is committed to building an education ecosystem in India - a Teacher Training Institute, a Lab School and a diversified Professional Learning Community, to help educators learn and practice the Art and Science of learning, teaching and leading.

FACTORS IMPACTING QUALITY OF EDUCATION

Quality in education is affected by a range of factors. While looking at quality in education practices, multiple facets need to be explored. The next section covers those factors that need to be kept in mind while building good quality schools. The section is an amalgamation of excerpts of conversations and experiences shared by some of the biggest changemakers in the field of education as well literature that has been drawn to supplant the prevailing narrative. These experts have been quoted verbatim at places in the document, and at some points, the learnings drawn have been written down inferentially. Having worked in diverse fields within the education sector, each expert advocated how one or several of the following nine aspects can be developed to transform quality in schools. Each of them have talked about strengthening schools using different approaches looking at different perspectives. These nine indicators are arrived at from collating narratives of the experts, however, not all have been discussed by each of them. While these are crucial in developing quality institutions, they must occur in simultaneous waves and one does not accord priority over the other.

I. Education among marginalised groups

The right to education mandates that 25% of students be representative of disadvantaged socio-economic groups. Despite incentives such as Mid-Day Meals and schemes like Samagra Shiksha being in place, the reality is starkly disturbing. As per the National Sample Survey Organisation's 2017-18 household survey, the number of out-of-school children in India between ages 6-17 years is 3.22 crore, a substantial portion of such children belong to socio-economically disadvantaged groups. Exclusion in classrooms will have long term ramifications on the socio-economic, political and demographic discourse in the country. The enrolments for Muslim students in higher secondary education was at 10% of the total enrolments in 2019-20. The proportion of enrolments declines with an increase in education levels. About 33% of students belonging to Scheduled Castes, Scheduled Tribes and Other Backward Classes drop out of state government schools in Class 10 (Department of School Education and Literacy, 2019-20).

Coleman (1990) affirms that “Educational equality is reached only when the results of schooling (achievement and attitudes) are the same for racial and religious minorities as for the dominant group”.

In India variation in the inputs received at successive levels of education translate into a stark variation in the educational output. There exists a huge contrast between the education received by the privileged class and that received by the marginalised. The well-equipped private schools are located mainly in metropolitan cities offering education services to the privileged, whereas the disadvantaged children are resigned to the fate of inadequate government schools. It is not possible to carry out any meaningful teaching-learning activity owing to the lack of minimum facilities leading to the low learning level of children attending these schools. Children coming from underprivileged backgrounds, most of them first-generation learners, also face difficulties in adjusting to the cultural differences between home and school (Bandyopadhyay, 2006).

Impact

Romana Shaikh believes that marginalisation shows up in classrooms, affects learning and outcomes. Children from difficult circumstances do not receive early childhood education and hence lack basic motor and neuro skills. They have neither seen role models nor have seen education make a difference to those in their community. Research confirms the value of “stable, responsive, nurturing relationships and rich learning experiences in the earliest years that provide lifelong benefits for learning, behavior and both physical and mental health” (Shonkoff and Richmond, 2009)

A World Bank report in May 2018 stated that the income of Indians is more dependent on their parents’ income and educational levels, restricting their chances of rising above the socio-economic strata they are born in (World Bank, 2018). Farhad Merchant is of the opinion that the socio-economically disadvantaged groups are faced with constraints of infrastructure and resources, the dearth of a congenial atmosphere in their homes along with the pressure to perform well. According to him the problem is compounded with the fact that most of these communities do not see education as an investment. Awareness and knowledge that education will help them move up the ladder, this missing awareness results in low aspirations.

Jyotsna Brar highlights that for the low-income groups, education is a luxury. Children from households with nomadic existence often have large gaps in learning. Children living in remote areas barely have access to schools. Prevalence of child labour and segregation of gender-based roles leads to higher drop-out rates among children from underprivileged backgrounds. As per NSSO (2014), about 53% of children between the ages of 5-15 drop out from school in urban areas and 60% of the same group drop out in rural areas. Moreover, parental illiteracy and language barriers add to the woes of children in difficult circumstances.

According to the Annual Status of Education Report (ASER) 2019, one in 10 rural children aged 14-18 years are unable to read a text in their own language meant for children aged 5-7 years. According to Brar, education infrastructure in rural areas is amiss. A huge one-size-fits-all approach makes it almost impossible for a child in a remote village to understand a textbook written in a metropolitan city. Patriarchy also denies girls from receiving meaningful education. As per the NSSO (2014), the gender gap in rural education is as high as 21%. Only 16% of children in Class 1 in 26 surveyed rural districts can read the text at the prescribed level, while almost 40% cannot even recognise letters (ASER, 2019).

What can be done?

Romana Shaikh suggests that learning should be tailored with consideration to the socio-economic environment. Educators must handle such children with more care and love, help the children find belief in themselves. Meeta Sengupta stresses the urgent need to sensitise faculty members on the nuances associated with differently-abled and underprivileged children. Education must become a high-quality process for vulnerable students. Policymakers need to define quality from the lens of the underprivileged as opposed to a rich and bright students' perspective. Enablement's and active supports put in place will reduce the exclusion faced by socio-economically disadvantaged groups. Technology must be specifically leveraged for the poor via specifically designed packages. Merchant believes that education is about mutual respect, collaboration and inclusion. If we are able to understand that each individual learns differently, it will foster an environment that each child is able to learn from the other. Kiran Bir Singh reiterates the point that

the education system treats everybody as a collective and that it must change.

'Diversity in schools helps you [students/teachers/administrators] to learn about inclusion, collaboration and working together to achieve creativity, critical thinking and life skills'.

- Farhad Merchant.

Vidyadhan Model

Vidyadhan is a flagship higher education scholarship program endorsed by the Shibulal Family Philanthropic Initiatives. Meritorious students from economically vulnerable backgrounds are provided financial support starting from standard XI till they complete graduation in a degree of their choice. Vidyadhan focuses on the holistic development of youth - preparing them with life skills and employability, thus putting them on track for professional growth.

The scholarship program has 88% of the students coming from financially deprived families, however, in the course of two years, 100% of them were able to bring their families out of poverty. The selection criterion is very meticulous, that includes academic performance, test interview, followed by home visits. The sponsorship program is for a graduate student but starts in Class XI. Besides the financial aspect of the program, there are training programs. Summer camps where students would get together for three or four days and the training would be basically in terms of guidance on life, learning, life and communication skill and career counselling at the graduation stage.

The program looks at students who might drop out after Class 10, intervenes and supports them so that they don't. Those selected will be eligible for two-year scholarship from the Foundation. If they continue to do well, they will be given a scholarship for pursuing any degree course of their interest. The scholarship amount for graduation courses varies from ₹ 10,000 to ₹ 60,000 per year depending on the state, course, duration etc.

Currently the Vidyadhan program has around 4300 students across the following states: Kerala, Karnataka, Tamil Nadu, Pondicherry, Andhra Pradesh, Gujarat, Maharashtra, Telangana, Goa and Odisha.

With inputs from Pankaj Tripathi

II. Early Childhood Care and Education

Research from disciplines such as neurobiology, economics, and child development has sufficient evidence to prove that the first few years are extremely crucial for life-long development, with most of the brain growth already complete by the time a child is five years old (Haartsen, Jone, & Johnson, 2016). The New Education Policy states that over 85 per cent of a child's brain develops by the age of 6 and stresses providing appropriate care and stimulation of the brain in a child's early years for healthy brain development and growth. The draft NEP 2019 believes the learning crisis occurs even before children enter Std I. Learning crisis occurs either because too many children enter formal schooling before six or too many children enter formal schooling without exposure to ECCE, hence lack readiness for rigours of formal schooling. The ASER 2019 'Early years' survey, indicated that more than 90% of children between ages 4-8 are enrolled in some institution. However, only 50% of students in grade I could perform numeric addition, and 40% could handle numeric subtraction. The survey reported that children's foundational skills improved in each subsequent grade. However, even by Grade III, a substantial percentage of all children were well behind where they were expected to be by the end of Std I (ASER, 2020).

Farhad Merchant highlighted that in the absence of appropriate intervention for early childhood care, children could lose out on crucial years of their lives. He also raises a concern that pre-primary education is not under the purview of a formal system and is largely unregulated. Jyotsna Brar believes that inadequate foundational learning coupled with the vast gap between pre-primary and primary education standards leads to a deterioration in the quality of education.

The Integrated Child Development Services (ICDS) program reaches over 8 million expectant and nursing women. It encompasses 76 million children in 1.26 million Anganwadi centres. ICDS amalgamates healthcare, nutrition and pre-school education into community-based child development centres. However, the program has been more focused on health and nutrition while largely neglecting the pre-school component.

III. Sports

Rekha Dey, a Sports for Development consultant, believes that sports can contribute immensely to inclusive and equitable quality education. By improving retention, it can help improve educational standards. Sports can empower women and girls and build leadership values.

ASER 2018 reported that about 80% of schools had a playground available for students, either inside the school premises or nearby. While 90% of schools in Himachal Pradesh, Haryana, and Maharashtra claimed to have a playground, more than a quarter of schools in Jammu and Kashmir, Bihar, Odisha, and Jharkhand did not have access to a playground. The report also highlighted a dearth of physical education teachers in rural areas, with only 5.8% of primary schools having a teacher. Only 55.8% of primary schools had some sort of sports equipment (ASER, 2019). According to Dey, In India, sports is only limited to elite schools; low budget or government schools are rarely associated with high engagement levels in sports. The way schools have cropped up in the urban area, the availability of open grounds is certainly a constraint.

Incorporating Sports in School

Sports for development has benefited the underprivileged by bringing sports and education together.

Dey feels that sports activities need to be evaluated and monitored to become outcome-driven. While the sector could benefit from investment, volunteer engagement for sports in school could also be explored. Sports must be a regular in the curriculum. The issue of open spaces can be solved by renting municipality grounds. Public-private partnerships and corporate social responsibility can be used to bring in sports facilities comparable to international standards.

Moreover, Dey is of the opinion that equipped sports centres with well-trained coaches could provide avenues for the youth and also employment generation. The relationship between a student and a coach is extremely crucial in streamlining sports into the curriculum. Dey says there are 242 existing jobs in the sports sector, and those need to be popularised to integrate sports at the school level. The myth that the employability of sports is only restricted to professional elite players must also be shattered.

IV. Skill Development

The New Education Policy aims at providing vocational skills to at least 50% of students by 2025 in such a way that the vocational skills acquired at the school level may be further extended up to higher education levels. Given that the educational decisions of youths are often linked to the educational-attainment level of their parents, participation in a vocational track might allow youths from a working-class background to pursue educational attainment beyond the compulsory level, hence increasing their chances of attaining skilled rather than unskilled employment (Shavit and Müller 1998).

Furthermore, with the separation of high- and low-type students, Vocational Education Training (VET) might counteract the equalising potential of vocational education (Shavit and Müller 2000). Given that only a few youths practically manage to enter academic education after vocational schooling, the vocational schooling option is often perceived as a dead-end track and second-choice education in many countries.

However, evidence from the US seems to indicate that, once selection into VET has been accounted for, its participants perform equally or better in terms of employment and wages than high school graduates, and these returns have increased over time. In contrast, evidence in the UK indicates that academic education leads to higher returns. (Kogan 2008, Carrero 2006).

Romana Shaikh believes that skills should provide students with gainful employment when the need arises, but also allow them to resume their academic pursuits as and when they can. According to Meeta Sengupta, spatial awareness that comes from training in carpentry, gardening is also critical for developing values such as leadership and innovation. The idea is to develop hands-on skills, which can be acquired along with academics and not just be restricted to employability.

Incorporating vocational education in curriculum

Sengupta is of the opinion that vocational education must meet expectations and aim for excellence. If vocational education is made mandatory, it should not be done with the idea of lowering expectations on the academic front. Shaikh reinstates that skilling is not a substitute for

poor academic performance. In Farhad Merchant's view, VET should be given the same degree of respect as a professional degree. He furthers with the example of German and Chinese trade schools where an apprentice has the same degree of respect as that of a professional degree holder.

German Trade School offer a dual-track program involving classroom-based learning in specialised trade schools as well as on-the-job work experience. Apprentices gain theoretical knowledge at a vocational school along with classes in German, English, and social studies.

Alongside which they also learn practical skills at a company or public sector institution. The trainees usually spend 60 percent of their time in the workplace under the supervision of a certified trainer and 40 percent in the classroom. More than a third of students graduating from secondary school in Germany opt for vocational training programs (Hockenos, 2018).

Vocational education in China is provided at three levels junior secondary, senior secondary and tertiary. Junior vocational education is vocational and technical education after primary school education and is a part of the 9-year compulsory education.

The Junior vocational system is aimed at training workers, peasants and employees in other sectors with basic professional knowledge and certain professional skills. These are mainly located in rural areas where the economy is less developed. Senior secondary schools are to produce secondary-level specialised and technical talents for the forefront of production, and students master the basic knowledge, theory and skills of their speciality in addition to the cultural knowledge required for higher school students. Tertiary schools are aimed at training secondary and high-level specialised technical and management talents needed in economic construction (Ministry of Education of the People's Republic of China, 2006).

V. Assessment and Evaluation

The process of assessment is used to determine the degree to which an individual child possesses a particular ability. The purpose of assessment is to understand a child's overall development. Moreover, it helps a teacher

to gauge whether a child is progressing within the academic system. Furthermore, assessment helps to identify children performing poor academically or who need special education services. Academic readiness tests, developmental screening tests, and diagnostic tests are forms of assessments. Evaluation on the other hand is the process of making judgments about the merit, value, or worth of educational programs, projects, materials, or techniques.

Romana Sheikh believes that exams are not helpful either to learners or to the teacher. The purpose of continuous evaluation is to understand progress and that learning is a continuous process. Continuous evaluation provides the idea that learning is about gaining feedback and thus using it to grow. Meeta Sengupta says that the assessment and evaluation in education should measure how much one has progressed from where one was. Tarun opines that the focus should be on allowing insight-based competition rather than trivia-based. Merchant feels that poor evaluation can increase learning gaps.

Jyotsna Brar says the language is a major barrier – parents, children and even teachers in several parts of the country have no familiarity with English and hence resort to rote learnings. In education, marks are regarded as the end-point and no one is actually assessing whether or not real learning is happening.

Gowri Iswaran reaffirms that academic performance is the end-all of the education system. Textbooks are looked on as the master, but they are only tools. The potential of each human being should not be confined simply to their grade card. Children should be allowed to find their own paths, and the education system must help them achieve those goals. Success should not be benchmarked by grades.

VI. Values in education

Schools play a crucial role in building and evolving the values children have already begun to develop by further introducing them to the values present in the society, such as equality and respect for diversity; and to help children to reflect, understand and apply values on their own (Halstead and Taylor, 2000).

Modernisation, economic and technological developments have resulted in intense competition among nations. Values of entrepreneurship,

competitiveness and individualism have assumed precedence over social cohesion and cooperation. Schools, too, have focused their energies to help individuals thrive in competition. Thereby, neglecting values such as friendship, respect, and cooperation that contribute to peace and fraternity (Gökçe, 2021). Umme Salma says, “Education must focus on improvement of students, see effort as a way to build their abilities and failure as a natural part of the learning process”.

Gowri Iswaran states that schools have the challenge to prepare children for jobs that have not yet been created, technology that has not been invented and problems that have not yet arisen. She also reaffirms the need to imbibe humanity in children by sensitising them to moral values and extending and developing the ability to face risks and uncertainty and follow one’s passion. Schools that marry competence and humanity will be able to produce fuller human beings. So far most schools have done a poor job of inculcating 21st-century skills such as innovation, collaboration and team spirit.

Iswaran believes that collaboration and teamwork, which are relatively easy to inculcate, have a whole bunch of side benefits. They allow the growth of other values such as integrity, trust and respect for others.

Moreover, whether or not the students and teachers feel comfortable and enjoy their time at school is equally important. Classrooms that are airy and have greenery around them help build student happiness. Furthermore, instilling gratitude in students will enable them to be good citizens willing to take responsibility.

According to Kiran Bir, schools reward students as long as they listen or repeat what is dictated by the authority. This learning experience creates citizens devoid of confidence and resigned to a fate of passivity and status quoists. Fear and passivity ingrained in young minds make learning less likely. Education must move from a space of fear or frustration to a space of optimism and creativity. The idea is to listen to the children rather than tell them. Looking at children with filters of age, gender, and other such demographic classifications diminish their potential. She suggests the use of design thinking in education to completely remove these filters to allow the creation of a humane framework and an I Can Mindset.

Singh believes that for values to be actionable, value education must be consistently routine in school timetables. A student must graduate with content and character. We treat all students like a collective and it must all go.

Schools need a coherent strategy for encouraging values in education. Empirical studies show bringing together a variety of teaching and learning approaches is much more effective in impacting the development of young people's values than adopting a single approach in isolation. There is a need to understand values development and methods of values education that needed to be imparted at the teacher training level (Halstead and Taylor, 2000).

Shaikh highlights that the goal of education is to allow learners to enquire into who they are. Tarun believes 'the higher aims of education involve looking at the inner potential of the learner and the lower aims are seeing education as means of livelihood generation. Utilitarian perspectives of learning are myopic'. The goal of education is to be a value-based mission. Education must create future leaders with a belief in culture, says Farhad Merchant.

Design thinking in Education

In order to find solutions to a problem, the idea is to engage with the people who are affected and afflicted and then craft a solution. The idea is to slow down and look at possibilities, find possibilities with the user. Whether it is looking at assessment or the spaces, it should not be done without the user. Design thinking is about reframing the user experience, understanding it and then activating the solution. Every stakeholder becomes a parent and incidental to the whole learning program. Localised solutions depend on what needs to be focussed on to improve the quality of education. Design thinking should engage students and allow them to explore different tools to create pragmatic and creative solutions to solve difficult problems and satisfy human wants. Moreover, design thinking can help develop teacher professionalism (Koh et. al, 2015).

With inputs from Kiran Bir Singh

VII. Technology in Education

Technology has immensely redefined education. Gowri Iswaran confirms that, with the advent of smartphones and the internet, the teacher is no longer the only person who gives out information to their students. The use of technology may very well give out more information, yet it by itself, cannot assure how that information is to be verified or used. This is now the job of the teacher. Technology has bridged the gap between teachers and students. A few teachers can reach a massive student population.

Jyotsna Brar highlights the huge digital divide in education. She feels that without proper training and infrastructure, the boon of technology cannot be utilised. While tech platforms can be used for teaching and professional learning, a vast majority of children do not have access to mobile devices.

Ritesh Singh, CEO , Eckovation also opines that a tech platform can greatly enhance the quality of educators. However, any technology solution deployed in education must have extensive reach. Apps that reach one-to-many, gauge responses to quizzes, understand the learning curve and give feedback can be transmitted to underserved areas. While may compromise with retaining students, but can ensure better inclusion. Moreover, digitising these responses can help to develop a learning curve.

However, the integration of technology needs an understanding of the entire psychology of the partners and the stakeholders. Headmasters, parents and students need to be on board. The whole model places teachers at the centre for content development and disbursement, which ensures sustainability. The program must be owned by the local stakeholders. So teachers, students and parents are involved very closely with the model. For unreachable areas in Bihar, Assam and Rajasthan, the contextualised content for these districts is available to be telecasted on Doordarshan, while it does not ensure individual attention, it at least allows for learning to happen in difficult circumstances.

Technology needs to be innovated to challenges in different regions. Mobile vans going into underserved regions, with teachers teaching students and then returning. Technology needs social reformation, understanding of stakeholders and end-users. End-users who may not be high on digital literacy, do not own laptops and need a simplified version

of the technology. Ritesh believes that if the tech solution is confined to mobiles, we may never come out of the digital divide. The solution should be defined or designed in a way where it facilitates one-to-many models of consumption of education.

Digital education can improve retention rates as well as provide standardised quality in education in the absence of quality teaching. Moreover, it allows to be teachers to be moderators while delivering a vast variety of content.

VIII. Parents

Kiran Bir believes that the education system in many ways serves parents rather than being an agent of change for children. Schools that have been extremely engaged with parents have their own pains, and schools that have been reluctant to engage with them have also seen their own set of challenges.

A parent body is a team that is genuinely appreciative and wants to make a difference, the school and parent body team learn to respect the decisions. A group of parents who love their children a lot, understand the why's, are happy to follow through with the what and how. The engagement between the parent body and school needs to be codified to develop a sense of trust and respect. A rational model rather than a defensive mechanism with parental cooperation for initiatives created will help sustain the chain of process.

IX. Teacher Training

Pankaj Jain describes what makes a good school - a good team of teachers, headed by a principal and has sound infrastructure. A good school combines the three elements in good measure.

Jain believes that policies ensure that teachers come with basic education and preparation of the mind. Certain necessary capabilities are mandated by policies and have been updated from time to time. The focus has been on teacher education and how to develop a good teacher education. Teacher qualification has been significantly high in India.

He goes on to explain that teacher incentives are seen in multiples of per capita income. OECD countries, on average, pay their teachers 1.2-1.8 times their respective per capita income. Developing countries such as

Indonesia pays an average of 3-4 times their per capita income. India pays an average of about 7-8 times its per capita income. Thus, India meets both qualification and incentives criteria.

Spending on Education

The OECD report on education claims that they spend 5-6% on education, including private and government spending. However, spending by society on education is one of the highest in India. (Both household and Government).

Jain goes on to list the problems that lie in the model of school we have tried to adopt/ implement.

He says we have relied on the formal education of teachers as the major input of a teacher's competency; however, much of the education takes place in the workforce. Teacher capacity cannot be developed with education. Degrees do not produce a better teacher.

He believes that the education system expects that teachers should hold fort in different subjects. The school system needs to mentor and supervise teachers for growth; the present school have small teams hence not conducive for the growth of teachers in the long run. The system is not designed for good teacher capability, despite incentives or teacher qualification.

Pankaj Jain is of the opinion that we will continue to have poor schooling performance unless the model changes. Furthermore, the traditional model of improving teacher capacity has been saturated – in-service training, pre-service norms and incentives will not produce remarkable results. A child will learn with even modest support and teacher quality.

He also feels that the curriculum design should be centred around the things that a child is being made to do in class alone or with peers. How is each activity of the child being planned and designed, what will a child listen to and what task he/she can perform alone or in partnership?

Pankaj Jain explains how the cost per child can be brought down-

The cost per child can be brought down with a modest-quality teacher and paying modest salaries. About 85% is the cost allotted to teachers. We do not need expensive teachers.

Further, he describes the abilities to be looked at while recruiting teachers:

- Cognitive capability
- How does the teacher relate to the child?
- The system must be pleasant to the teacher.

He suggests training high school students to become teachers. The teacher training curriculum has limited functionality; the useful part is limited and can be covered in less time. Following this approach can drastically cut down on teacher training costs.

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WHAT MAKES A GOOD SCHOOL?

This section take a case study approach to understand the journey's undertaken by different schools in a bid to bring quality to education practices. The team had come up with an exhaustive list of schools covering diverse curriculums, mediums, managements among other markers. However, the outbreak of the pandemic and the closure of schools as well as difficulties faced by the schools during these times were a major impediment in covering all those schools in the list. Hence, the schools listed below are the ones that allowed CDPP to conduct this research and were open about their practice.

AL FALAH SCHOOL

Year of Establishment	2011
Name of the Trust / Society	Al Falah Educational Trust
Founder	Fouzia Khan
Teacher / Student Ratio	1:25
No. of Students	1200
Board	CBSE
Medium of Instruction	English
Minority / Non-Minority	Non-Minority
Private / Govt.	Private
Boys / Girls / Co-ed	Co-education

HISTORY / EVOLUTION: EARLY DAYS, GROWTH PHASE, PRESENT STATUS:

Al Falah School was founded in June 2011 by Dr. Fouzia Khan, an educator at the core. She picked up five orphan children from the street with the intent to make them educated and successful. The school undoubtedly reflects her farsighted vision for the cause of education. She believes in inclusive education as the key to human enrichment and India's giant strides to progress. Al Falah has state of the art facilities and infrastructure to support her vision and endeavour to make education a holistic and pleasant experience. The hostel at Al Falah is accommodated with a hundred orphan

kids, both boys and girls. The student strength at Al Falah (2021-2022) is 1200 students. It is recognised by the Central Board of Secondary Education (CBSE). The school lays a strong foundation for character building and academic excellence among students so that they deal with the challenges of the future.

The school's mission is to prepare each student for academic, social and personal growth by creating a community of empowered and diverse learners, striving to be cosmopolitan citizens in an atmosphere of mutual respect, understanding and trust. The administration, staff, and students are committed to this mission and work together to obtain exceptional academic, co-curricular and extracurricular results at this day-boarding cum residential School.

Al Falah School has an idyllic setting, a sprawling campus amidst hills and fields, favourable weather, and a pollution-free atmosphere. The students are able to learn, observe, introspect and evolve in a serene atmosphere. Education in such an ambience is a rewarding experience for their students. Al Falah aims to provide a solid foundation by developing the child intellectually as well as socially, morally, physically and emotionally by providing a stimulating, nurturing and relaxed environment. Al Falah attempts to bridge the gap between the comfortable environs of a child's home and the rigours of formal education. Their passion is to turn education into a beautiful voyage of discovery.

They have some unique programs in place. Their emphasis is on equipping students with knowledge of basics. Moreover, they have an English language drive where students systematically develop their vocabulary and learn new words with great ease. Another novel feature at Al Falah is teaching life skills and moral science concepts together with academic concepts. They have a 'perfect tarbiyat (teaching etiquette and manners) program' to help their students improve life skills.

Most of their teachers are first-aid trained and regularly attend professional development workshops. The teaching methods and interactive classrooms are vital elements in creating a healthy and safe environment. They have a strict policy on discipline and separate blocks for boys and girls. Al Falah boasts of a well-endowed library, an equipped pre-primary section and a science lab, a range of sports activities with indoor and outdoor facilities.

Although a rigorous academic program is at the core of everything, the school has an equally outstanding co-curricular and extracurricular agenda for students that provides much-needed holistic education.

Learnings

If given the education ecosystem at par with regular students, children from underprivileged roots can achieve similar outcomes in learning. An emphasis on strengthening fundamentals is often lost in the rat race to achieve perfect scores. However, Al Falah's attempt to empower students with basics is noteworthy. Their special program to develop values along with academic excellence is of particular significance given the falling standards of morals and ethics.

AZAAN INTERNATIONAL SCHOOL

Year of Establishment	2006
Name of the Trust / Society	Anwarunnissa Charitable Trust
Founder	Chairman - Mohammed Yousuf Azam
Student / Teacher Ratio	1:14
No. of Students	800+
Board	Central Board of Secondary Education (CBSE)
Medium of Instruction	English
Minority / Non-Minority	Minority Institution
Private / Govt.	Private
Boys / Girls / Co-ed	Boys and Girls Study in the same campus with segregated classes

HISTORY/EVOLUTION: EARLY DAYS, GROWTH PHASE, PRESENT STATUS:

The school was started with a vision to provide education together with values to help students become productive citizens of the society. Many schools that offer good education often miss out on producing a fuller and more well-rounded human being. At AIS, both these aspects are well-integrated within the schooling system.

The school has registered impressive growth and owes its spectacular success to the able leadership, diligent governance, the experience of its governing board and the unflinching support from the parents.

The focus on value-based education, regular meetings and training opportunities enable teachers to become role models and lead by example. The management undertakes regular supervision to ensure that the assimilation of values happens along with the curriculum. The focus is to help hone the innate talents of students along with their spiritual and moral quotient. The end goal is to groom a spiritually & intellectually superior future generation.

The school's efforts have been recognised and awarded by various renowned agencies like British Council – ISA and the Education Asia group for Innovation in Education.

Learnings

The emphasis on moral values has been consistent at Azaan International; constant efforts have been undertaken to ensure that spiritual and moral growth happen alongside academics. Teachers are supported with subject-specific workshops, value-based workshops and teaching. All Teachers are encouraged to use teaching aids and make the classes interesting. Live classes held during the pandemic were interactive to ensure students retain their interest in the online mode of learning. School had cut down fees, provided 100% fee discount for orphans and several scholarships to deserving students to help ease the burden of the parents during the pandemic. A particularly important takeaway is that despite the lack of an adequately sized ground, the student's physical development is taken care of with the support of physical education experts from Edusports. Apart from daily physical routines, the facilities offer sports enthusiasts expert coaching in various disciplines.

A contentious issue revealed by AIS was their relationship with the student's parents. The school has a tough time dealing with the casual attitude of parents with regards to payment of fees and responsibilities towards the school. The parent community does not regard education as an investment.

CHOWRAHA JINSI GOVT. PRIMARY SCHOOL

Year of Establishment	-
Name of the Trust / Society	-
Founder	-
Student / Teacher Ratio	1:25
No. of Students	170
Board	SSC
Medium of Instruction	Urdu
Minority / Non-Minority	Non-Minority
Private / Govt.	Govt.
Boys / Girls / Co-ed	Co-ed

HISTORY/EVOLUTION: EARLY DAYS, GROWTH PHASE, PRESENT STATUS:

This Chowraha Jinsi Govt. Primary School is a typical Govt. school in Hakeempet, Hyderabad, without proper infrastructure. There was no boundary wall or a gate. The school would house rag-pickers and hooligans in the evening until the teachers and students came to school the following day.

The absence of toilets or clean drinking water kept even the most eager students stay away. The floors used to be cleaned by students who made it to school and their teachers. Mid-day meals were probably the reason these poor students attended school despite all odds.

Access Foundation – a local NGO took the initiative to work with the school and meet the parents of the 150 enrolled students. Access collaborated with an MNC Cognizant Technology Solutions to conduct a clothing and blanket distribution drive, which attracted several parents. Parents were received by about 20 counsellors to understand the mindset and figure out reasons apart from the obvious ones and address them.

The lack of toilets was one of the primary reasons why students, especially girls, stayed away from attending school. These parents preferred that their children work in small scale industries and earn wages rather than attending

school. The NGO coordinated with the local MLA and Govt. body to provide basic facilities in the school. The partnership with Cognizant's Outreach – CSR put the school back in shape. Hard and consistent work from Cognizant volunteers each week, NGOs support and hard-working teachers could bring an unbelievable change in the school.

The Government, the local MLA, the GHMC Counsellor, Cognizant and Access Foundation transformed the primary school, and the building could even host the high school classes/students, which would earlier run in a rented space in the nearby area.

Learnings

Facilities such as clean toilet, potable drinking water, decent classroom structures can go a long way in improving enrolment and retention rates. Chowraha Jinsi is a prime example of how a school's partnership with civil society and CSR networks can transform the existing infrastructure into a conducive learning environment. The school is also a fine example of how placing children and mothers at the centre of policy interventions increases enrollments and participation.

CREEKSIDE INTERNATIONAL SCHOOL

Year of Establishment	2010
Name of the Trust / Society	Qamar Education Society
Founder	Chairman - Mohammed Misbahuddin
Student / Teacher Ratio	1:11
No. of Students	500
Board	CBSE
Medium of Instruction	English
Minority / Non-Minority	Minority
Private / Govt.	Private
Boys / Girls / Co-ed	Co-ed

HISTORY/EVOLUTION: EARLY DAYS, GROWTH PHASE, PRESENT STATUS:

The school is situated in the outskirts of the city with an ample space and infrastructure. The school was set up with the intention of catering to both academic and life skills. The founder set up the school to impart quality education along with Quranic and Arabic education. The founder's vision was to produce balanced human beings. The school started with 6 students in 2010 and presently has 500 students studying in it. Many skill development programmes are introduced in the school to develop life skills among students. It is a centre of excellence for value-based education.

Creekside International School is spread across a lush and green 3.5-acre campus. The classrooms are bright and airy with a good teacher-student ratio. The school has indoor and outdoor games, a well-equipped lab and audio-visual rooms.

There is a particular focus on weak students to streamline the slow learners. Special classes are conducted for such students. The primary teachers are provided assistant teachers with the purpose of giving individual attention to each student. The students are taken for the field trips twice a year. Students attend Olympiads and have won at the state level. The school has had 100% results so far. Special fee concessions are given to the students from financially challenged backgrounds.

Learnings

The school uses skilling classes to build confidence and promote all-round development of students. Parents need to be counselled for them to see education as an investment.

FOCUS HIGH SCHOOL

Year of Establishment	2013
Name of the Trust / Society	Jafaria Institute of Social Medicine
Founder	Minhaj Arastu
Student / Teacher Ratio	1:16
No. of Students	1200
Board	IB / SSC
Medium of Instruction	English
Minority / Non-Minority	Non-Minority
Private / Govt.	Private
Boys / Girls / Co-ed	Co-ed

HISTORY/EVOLUTION: EARLY DAYS, GROWTH PHASE, PRESENT STATUS:

Focus was founded by a group of philanthropic businessmen and professionals who wanted to provide access to high quality, holistic education in the Old City of Hyderabad in 2013. The founder of the school is Minhaj Arastu. It is under Jafaria Institute of Social Medicine (JISM) which is the registered society that works in the health and education. Focus has two campuses, with primary classes at Noor Khan Bazar and secondary classes at Darushifa. The infrastructure is designed for safety, supporting effective teaching and learning.

The school has built a conducive learning environment based on understanding and respect. They have an open house every week. Focus is a community that engages all stakeholders in the pursuit of knowledge. Focus students do not simply consume knowledge produced by others; instead, they create understanding and develop inquiry, reflection, self-management, collaboration, and listening skills. Students are expected to be committed participants in society. In fact, guests who interact with focus students are impressed with the questions and energy of the children.

Teachers at Focus are the campaigners of life-long learning for students. Each year the school organises and takes part in numerous seminars for professional development. Teachers are encouraged and supported to

pursue courses and conferences that will help them to inspire children. The faculty boasts of a CENTA certified teacher, an all-India topper in the Teaching Professionals Olympiad, and dozens of teachers pursuing further education and certifications. An internship program is the centrepiece of their learning community, through which they induct new members into the teaching profession with the guidance and support of lead teachers.

Focus does not limit itself to textbooks and examinations alone; instead, it strives for the holistic development of children within the framework of the International Baccalaureate Primary Years Programme and the Telangana State secondary curriculum. Focus High School is the only IB authorised school in the Old City, a significant accomplishment given IB's demanding standards.

The teachers at Focus tirelessly work to stoke curiosity in children's minds and put together thought-provoking experiences. The school nurtures and challenges the high achieving students by encouraging them to participate in various interschool events. Focus seeks to widen access to IB programmes in several ways. Thus, the fee structure is such that common people can afford the costs. The school provides for students' holistic development - encouraging students to be critical and creative thinkers; guiding them to be principled and compassionate; training them for physical health; and preparing them for higher studies and employment. Convinced that education is a means of establishing justice and mercy in the world, Focus High School ensures that its programmes are accessible to all.

Learnings

Each members of the Focus community seeks to improve, learn, and grow. Focus strives for the integrated development of children's intellectual, emotional, social, spiritual, and physical aspects of life. According to Focus, learning is a process of "constructing, testing and revising mental models of how the world works, and it is this process that enables each student to make meaning of their lives and the world around them". The school serves male & female children of varied communities, economic backgrounds, and academic abilities, this diversity allows for the growth of mutual tolerance and respect. Leadership in the school is distributed and devolved, relying on the active

collaboration of creative and reflective teachers. The school is conscientiously trying to support each student as per their needs. Focus High School is the only IB authorised school in the Old City, a significant accomplishment given IB's demanding standards. Focus, like many other schools, also faces problems with parental cooperation.

GLENDALE INTERNATIONAL SCHOOL

Year of Establishment	2003
Name of the Trust / Society	Hyderabad Educational Academy
Founder	Basheer Uddin Babukhan
Student / Teacher Ratio	1:20
No. of Students	3000
Board	CBSE / IB
Medium of Instruction	English
Minority / Non-Minority	Non-minority
Private / Govt.	Private
Boys / Girls / Co-ed	Co-ed

HISTORY/EVOLUTION: EARLY DAYS, GROWTH PHASE, PRESENT STATUS:

Glendale Academy was envisioned by Basheer Uddin Babukhan, who was already running a chain of schools called Springfields. A well-known politician and a philanthropist, he established an unconventional school called Glendale Academy in 2003.

Anjum Babukhan, the school director, intended to create lifelong learners, having a twin focus on building academic competence and character. She found the educational system in India outdated, rigid and incompetent for the same.

Glendale offers an environment that exposes young minds to mental stimulation and physical strength. The expansive playground with a petting zoo provides students with opportunities to explore a variety of sports, develop team and competitive spirit, and learn compassion.

Empathy and inclusiveness are crucial to the pedagogy at Glendale Academy. Their belief is that 'The more ways they teach, the more children they reach'. The school also aims to develop desirable traits such as responsibility, generosity and compassion through innovative learning methods.

The RRC- Respect, Responsibility and Cooperation culture along with the integration of United Nations Sustainable Development goals and the concept of the 'Leader in Me' has helped to sow the seeds of character in young minds. Dr. Howard Gardner's Multiple Intelligence methodology, Eric Jensen's Brain-Compatible Learning Strategies and the Cs of the 21st century are some critical elements used while devising learning strategies.

The teachers at Glendale undergo a rigorous professional development program at regular intervals. This program aims to make the teachers acquainted with practical and innovative teaching trends.

Learnings

The school curriculum is innovative and scientifically designed. Multiple Intelligence is integrated into their curriculum to develop the innate potential of each child. The school believes that "the more ways they teach, the more children they reach. Glendale has a unique philosophy of internationally researched methodologies that integrates academics, personality development and universal human values for the holistic growth of their students.

HYDERABAD PUBLIC SCHOOL

Year of Establishment	1972
Name of the Trust / Society	Hyderabad Public School Society
Founder	Seventh Nizam of Hyderabad – Mir Osman Ali Khan
Student / Teacher Ratio	1:23
No. of Students	2300
Board	CBSE
Medium of Instruction	English
Minority / Non-Minority	Non-Minority
Private / Govt.	Private
Boys / Girls / Co-ed	Co-ed

HISTORY/EVOLUTION: EARLY DAYS, GROWTH PHASE, PRESENT STATUS:

HPS Begumpet was established by Mir Osman Ali Khan in the year 1923. After a period of fifty years, in the year 1972, another branch of Hyderabad Public School was established in Ramanthapur, Hyderabad, on 40 acres of land. The school is managed by The Hyderabad Public School Society through its Board of Governors. It has over 2300 students from pre-primary through 12th. The teacher-student ratio is 1:23 and the school is affiliated with the Central Board of Secondary Education. The school is an ethical, non-profitable, co-educational institution.

Hyderabad Public School aims to provide holistic education, where each child is a valued partner. The child is facilitated to achieve his or her optimum potential to meet the challenges of life, enabling him or her to be a global citizen and future leader. The mission of HPS is to improve the students' communication skills, instil a sense of respect for others and the environment while being appreciative of individual differences at the same time. They prepare the students for life and aim at inculcating value-based education that nurtures the young learners inside and out. HPS Ramanthapur has been ranked number 3 in Telangana and Number 12 in the country by education world.

HPS believes in incorporating technology and innovation in education.

When learners readily adopt and adapt technology, the learning experience is transformed. At HPS, the aim is to build a holistic learning environment that plays a significant role in the cognitive development of the students. The school has established collaborative practices in which teachers and students are co-learners. The school has tried to shift away from traditional delivery towards a more student-centric and constructive model, project-based learning in which the teacher is a guide. The focus is increasingly on participation and deliberation rather than direction and instruction. The school believes in the democratisation of education, an approach in education that is done with and by learners rather than done to them. The institutions aims to build capacity through interdependence.

HPS stresses the necessity to incorporate life skills along with reading, writing and arithmetic - communication skills, goal setting, decision-making, conflict resolution, interpersonal and critical thinking are imparted. The school also focuses immensely on peer-group interaction and the learnings that are gained through group activities. The skills that the students learn in such engagements greatly enhance their academic performance and help them interact better with friends, family members and eventually at their workplaces.

To motivate this generation to be leaders of tomorrow, HPS is committed to developing leadership skills that allow children to think big, speak their minds, take the initiative, analyse information, and manage time and money, thereby making them successful learners and active citizens.

Learnings

HPS has students from diverse backgrounds, allowing children to learn and overcome differences. HPS has gained the 'Highest Happiness Quotient' with parents. Professional development via training sessions for teachers is encouraged. HPS follows the flip-board method that helps impart innovative ideas and practical learning. HPS believes in instilling leadership as the end goal of school education. They often use the power of their stellar alumni to conduct engaging sessions for their students.

IQRA MISSION HIGH SCHOOL

Year of Establishment	1986
Name of the Trust / Society	Iqra Education Society
Founder	Mohammed Sajid Ali
Student / Teacher Ratio	1:25
No. of students	1800+
Board	Secondary School Certificate (S.S.C.) Telengana State Board
Medium of Instruction	English
Minority / Non-Minority	Minority Institution
Private / Govt.	Budget Private School
Boys / Girls / Co-ed	Co-Edu

HISTORY/EVOLUTION: EARLY DAYS, GROWTH PHASE, PRESENT STATUS:

In the early days of its establishment, the focus was on the school's growth and making it acceptable to the demands of a neighbourhood living below the poverty. The school managed to gain ground through various tedious yet successful efforts to create trust and a zeal for learning.

The school adopted several measures to ensure quality education at an affordable price. The emphasis was on making a generation literate to ensure upward mobility of the community. Steadily the school inched towards its vision and churned successful students year after year. A special coaching program after school, an overhaul of school policies to suit the stakeholders' expectations, counselling and dialogue with the parent community to help support learners through home interventions are a part of the success story of this school.

Owing to the pandemic the school has faced drawbacks in the learners' attitudes and school finances. The school's finances have been stretched to hire and retain staff that can deliver better teaching and learning experiences. The school is facing financial pressure as it serves low-income groups with an affordable fee structure and is finding it difficult to hire good teachers who demand higher salaries.

Learnings

Visionary leadership of the school correspondent has helped contribute in raising awareness and educating students belonging to the underprivileged community (daily wage workers). Good quality education at a reasonable cost. Teachers are well supported with a series of in-house training programmes to adopt novel teaching techniques. Senior faculty often model the best practices during the staff development sessions.

The school staff has filmed concept videos to enable students to access the lessons conveniently through their website. This has benefitted the enrolled students and those students who have missed schooling due to the pandemic. The school charges fees for ten months from students and has one of the most economical fee structures amongst budget private schools in the old city area. The students get a wide range of exposure through meaningful field trips to places around Hyderabad, ensuring exposure and newer perspectives.

MADINA PUBLIC SCHOOL

Year of Establishment	1980
Name of the Trust / Society	The Madina Education and Welfare Society
Founder	K.M. Arifuddin
Student / Teacher Ratio	1:15
No. of Students	1800
Board	CBSE
Medium of Instruction	English
Minority / Non-minority	Minority
Private / Govt.	Private
Boys / Girls / Co-ed	Co-edu

HISTORY/EVOLUTION: EARLY DAYS, GROWTH PHASE, PRESENT STATUS:

The school is situated in the heart of the city. Started in the year 1982, the school has played a pivotal role in raising the standards of education for Muslim minorities in particular and all other communities in general. From a humble beginning, Madina has made tremendous strides over the years under the inspiration of one selfless and dedicated visionary. The enormous response and demand for good education in the twin cities led to the origin of Madina Public School.

Islamic values and ethics are an integral part of the school and in accordance with the parents' wishes. Madina's emphasis is not simply on literacy but on meaningful education, catering to the challenges of the present society. The school is now at par with missionaries and corporate schools in the twin cities and has achieved 100% results for the last 36 years.

The school has both the parent and student counsellors for guidance and support. Madina successfully transformed itself from SSC to CBSE syllabus. The mission of the school is to establish a centre of innovative learning where teachers collaborate with students in developing pedagogical applications. The students are given the opportunity to use the latest technology in education to develop problem-solving and critical thinking skills across the curriculum. Co-curricular activities are given equal importance, all the students need to participate in activities held in the school.

Apart from academics, the school believes in instilling civic sense and social responsibility. Regular teacher training programs are organised for the teachers as a continuous process. Mini-workshops for the students are organised to help them build concentration, memory and learning skills.

Learnings

The students are given the opportunity to use the latest technology to develop problem solving and critical thinking skills across the curriculum. The co-curricular activities are given equal importance, all the students need to participate in activities held in the school. The attempt to inculcate civic sense and social responsibility is particularly significant. Training program for teachers and workshops for students is a remarkable idea to keep the process of learning continuous.

MOUNT MERCY SCHOOL

Year of Establishment	1999
Name of the Trust / Society	Al-Asr Educational Society
Founders	Indian Professionals working in Saudi Arabia
Student / Teacher Ratio	1:17
No. of students	800
Board	SSC
Medium of Instruction	English
Minority / Non-Minority	Non-minority
Private/Govt.	Private
Boys/Girls/Co-ed	Co-ed

HISTORY/EVOLUTION: EARLY DAYS, GROWTH PHASE, PRESENT STATUS:

After lengthy deliberations, a group of Indian professionals working in Saudi Arabia concluded that the emancipation of the Muslim community lies in education. The other major conclusion was that there is a need to provide quality education at an affordable cost, and the discussion yielded shape in the form of Mount Mercy School which was inaugurated in the year 1999.

The school management believes in equality, respect for all faiths and creeds and social justice. The aim of the school is to develop a responsible attitude among children to make them independent.

At Mount Mercy, a combination of approaches are used to give the best learning experience to the students. While academics are given their due importance, attention is also accorded to nurturing various talents among children.

MMS is a co-educational Institute from pre-primary to 10th. It follows the state syllabus and is recognised by the government of Andhra Pradesh. Moreover, has been achieving excellent results in the SSC examination. It is housed in a three-storey structure with lively interiors. An open space of 1000 sq. m in front of the building is used as a playground.

The school has always given due attention to technology and introduced digital learning or smart learning in 2013. Each floor is equipped with a smartboard used for students from UKG to 10th. This new audio-visual aid has brought about a major change in teaching. The students have taken up to digital learning enthusiastically.

The principal plays an essential role in improving the quality of the school. The school's strength is 800 students, and the teacher-student ratio is 1:17. The principal takes up home visits to find out the issues faced by the slow learners. Regular counselling sessions for children, parents and families are held to help them identify shortcomings and overcome them. They believe that if a child is happy at heart, he is an achiever; hence, a significant focus is on making a child 'happy' rather than on marks. The house visits by the principal and teachers did help in improving the standards of the child's performance.

Empathy is a trait instilled among students at MMS through prayers, Joy of Giving, Joy of sharing and special assemblies. The school successfully collected the amount of rupees 2.5 lacs from the students for a school child who was sick and needed money for his treatment. Foodgrains and money are collected from the students for the deserving people. A few financially underprivileged students are given meals in school. MMS believes in providing opportunities to all regardless of income - 400 students were allowed to take online classes despite not paying the fees.

The school has an open house every Saturday, where the talents and achievements of students are showcased. The children have demonstrated a praiseworthy performance in academics, oration, essay writing, arts, dramatics, music and sports. A remarkable surge in their confidence levels and self-esteem was seen after the children started participating in various contests and inter-school competitions. A school development plan exists and more than a majority of the plan is followed.

Multiple teacher training programs are organised, and regular assessment of the teachers is one of the many practices adopted to maintain the standard of the teaching staff. The principal herself meets with the staff every Saturday after the open house where various issues and their solutions are discussed. Peer teaching and training is encouraged at MMS. The school is equipped

with science and math labs, a library, digital classes and proper sports facilities. Both curricular and co-curricular activities are given equal importance. The school imparts martial arts and defence training for both girls and boys.

MMS had 26 specially-abled children in the school, and a trained teacher was appointed to help them. These students were placed according to their age in the classes and a substantial change was noticed in the growth and development of these children when they were placed with the regular kids.

For Mount Mercy School, education means leading a healthy and happy life, and the school champions this cause in their everyday practice.

Learnings

For a child to be successful, he/she must be happy at heart. The school believes that a child's happiness at home and school, is an important determinant for his/her success. The home visits by the principal herself, is a noteworthy intervention and helps in understanding a child's overall well-being. It is remarkable how the school has integrated specially-abled children in regular classrooms. In this world driven by competition and hunger for success, the school tries to inculcate the value of empathy among the students through carefully crafted activities. Multiple teacher training programs are organised and regular assessment of the teachers is one of the many practices adopted to maintain the standard for the teaching staff.

PRINCESS ESIN GIRLS' HIGH SCHOOL

Year of Establishment	In 1971, a lab school was established for students seeking a Diploma in Pre - School education, became a full - fledged school in 2001
Name of the Trust / Society	Nizamia Hyderabad Women's Association Trust
Founder	Prince Mufakkham Jah and Princess Esin
Student / Teacher Ratio	1:25
No. of Students	2700 Approximately
Board	CISCE (Council for Indian School Certificate Examination)
Medium of Instruction	English
Minority / Non-Minority	Minority
Private / Govt.	Private
Boys / Girls / Co-ed	Girls' School

HISTORY/EVOLUTION: EARLY DAYS, GROWTH PHASE, PRESENT STATUS:

Princess Esin's Girls' High School was founded almost 40 years ago. At that time, the general populace was conservative and reluctant to educate women. They wanted to marry their girls at a young age, given that there were not many safe and secure educational centres. It was a difficult decision for most parents to send their daughters to study at prominent educational institutes which were located far from the old city area. The visionary founders, concerned with illiteracy in the community, started the Nizamia Hyderabad Women's Association Trust.

The trust started a vocational centre that provided a teaching diploma to the local girls. The girls could then take up teaching positions in the city schools, a vocation acceptable amongst the under-privileged conservative families of the old city. The institution attempted to raise the academic and economic standards of the community.

The school is located in the heritage buildings belonging to the family of the last Nizam of Hyderabad. The descendants of the royal family sought to use the building for the purpose of providing affordable and good quality schools for girls. After the 'Teachers Training Institute', a 'Lab School' was started which admitted students from the neighbouring areas. With classes being added each year the strength has now reached approximately 2700 students. The school has added an extension block to accommodate its students.

Learnings

The curriculum has a blend of coursework and vocational subjects like cooking and (Socially Useful Productive work) SUPW work which equips young students with skills for life. A dedicated team of teachers has served in this institution for two decades. Some alumni of this institution also serve as teachers. Teachers are regularly trained to help them keep abreast with the latest teaching concepts. Teachers are suitably paid and enjoy benefits related to continued service, which ensures job satisfaction. High school students receive need-based and merit-based scholarships as an incentive to complete their school education. All orphans receive a 100% scholarship. Steady and robust leadership has helped transform education for girls in the Old City of Hyderabad.

Challenges faced by these schools

- In most schools, the attitude of parents is an enabling factor in providing quality education. Most schools highlighted that parent does not see education as an investment, which in turn impacts fee collection and subsequently budgetary allocations.
- Despite teacher training programs, improving teaching quality has been a major hurdle for most schools.
- Quality cannot be imbibed in schools which have failed to bring disadvantaged children on par with the rest of the class. Most schools have still not been able to adopt an approach that strengthens inclusion and diversity.
- While infrastructure is a prerequisite for receiving boards affiliations, there is a general disconnect between utilisation of the resources and the utility of it in learning system. The challenge of the future lies in integrating state of the art infrastructure with the fundamental learning ecosystem.

The Indian school system is still heavily reliant on scoresheets and grades to assess the worth of a student and learning processes, this is a major reason for the lack of quality in schools,

- There is an obvious disconnect between the child's need, the parents' expectation and the school's capacity, this will continue to pose a challenge for Indian school system in the coming years.
- The hour's need is in developing 21st-century skills like empathy, collaboration, teamwork, innovation, creativity. The apparent downside in our present system is the lack of focus on values.

Do's

- A good school must acknowledge the socio-economic inequities among its students but consciously make an effort to empower students coming from difficult circumstances. While assimilating these differences, the schools must also ensure that students learn to thrive and co-exist in a non-homogenous system. A school environment that fosters these differences, will also help students learn from these differences. Education must be tailored to suit the needs of a diverse set of minds, provide the care and instill faith. A school by way of targeted interventions and active supports can reduce the exclusion faced by socio-economically disadvantaged groups.
- For a school to perform well and achieve excellence, support from parents is an essential factor. Parents need to see education as an investment and not a burden. A school must form an association with parents, probably by way of active parent groups. This allows schools to develop interventions centered around parents. For instance, the Aga Khan group of schools, in order to reduce screen time for children, trained parents to deliver the educational content to their children.
- The incorporation of vocational training skills can help students develop attitudes such as dexterity and concentration. VET can be imparted as essential life skills.
- While most schools believe in inculcating values among their students, a school must have a coherent strategy to make learning a value laced experience. A good school must embed value in its teachings, have a specially designed program for the same and make an effort to monitor the percolation of a rich value system among its students.

- A good school must take semi-trained teachers, mentor and supervise them to curate a curriculum centered around children.
- A good school must have visionary leadership that is able to translate primary resources such as infrastructure and human resources into a centre of learning and growth.
- Technology in education is being explored by schools more so after the pandemic. A school is must provide technology solutions suited to the needs of the school. During the pandemic, several schools were able to transition to a digital platform. However, many of their students were without devices. Moreover, children in remote parts of the country had no access to education. While most schools are able to deploy technology in their teaching, a good school is one that is able to innovate a technological model to provide last-mile connectivity.
- A good school should allow students to pick, choose and learn at their own pace. Good quality becomes the culture when a school has good processes in place.
- Schools must focus on foundational learning. The gap between pre-primary and primary education needs to be bridged. Pre-primary education is largely unregulated, this often creates learning gaps and schools must intervene to iron them out.
- A school must focus on incorporating language skills, soft skills training, writing, and research skills in mainstream education practice.
- A good school uses extra-curricular activity to build team spirit and healthy competition among its students.
- A school should prepare its student for the future and equip them with career guidance, so they're able to make the right choices after school.

Above all, a good school believes in the happiness of children and thus treats each child as an individual. Their systems are designed by the children and for the children. Satisfied children help institutions deliver results.

Don'ts

- Marks should not be taken as barometer of success. The school must see the progress of the child in terms of where they have come from and where they are now.

- Schools must stop treating students as a collective, and listen to children's need rather than telling them.
- Schools need to realise that technology cannot be deployed without taking into account the needs and constraints of the students. Smart boards seem widely popularised, it is important to ascertain whether actual learning and retention happen whilst using it.
- Schools must distance themselves from being solely focused on academic excellence and move towards creating leaders and human beings with exceptional life skills.
- While several schools believe that modern and premium infrastructure helps them attract students and retain them, it still does not guarantee quality in learning and education practices. An infrastructure-led cost heavy model must give way to one which pools or shares resources. Be it a playground, qualified teachers or a library if schools in a vicinity are able to share these resources, a far more sustainable, cost-effective and efficient approach can be developed.
- Moral values cannot and should not be treated as a school subject requiring separate classes, but rather be embedded in everyday learning and curriculum. Students must learn by doing rather than do by learning.
- Vocational education taught in school should not be done to lower expectations or as recourse to poor academic performance.
- A good school should not compromise on ethics.
- The failure of a school stems from the constant attention given to the best students while neglecting the weakest. A school should not solely focus on nurturing its best talent.
- A school cannot work only by fostering competition, what it needs to build is cooperation among its students and also teachers.
- A good school must avoid poor quality teachers.
- The focus of a school should not be on rote learning rather on knowledge creation.

Framework for Quality Education

- Enabling School Environment
 - Trained teachers
 - Early Childhood Care and Education
 - Technology in Education
 - Sports Development
 - Skill Development
- Enabling Policy Environment
 - Inclusion in school processes
 - Stakeholder engagement in policy-making processes
 - Pooling of infrastructure and resources
 - Streamlining Assessment and Curriculum practices
- Enabling Home and Community Environment
 - Parental Education
 - Values in education

SECTION - 2

A LOST YEAR – THE IMPACT OF COVID-19 ON SCHOOL GOING CHILDREN

About Forty-one percent of our population is below 20 years of age. This makes up for a sizeable chunk of the school-going population in need of education and skills for a robust workforce in the future. Nearly 1.5 million schools were shut in India for 315 days, a significant part of 2020 and early 2021, due to the pandemic impacting about 250 million children. With the second wave now gripping the country, most schools are closed once again, with year-end exams cancelled or postponed. The pandemic has exacerbated concerns of equity and equality in several aspects of life, access to education being a significant one.

Across 190 countries, 1.7 billion students were affected by the closure of educational establishments. While the advanced nations had the means and the method to offer remote learning to their students, the low-income countries faced several challenges in offering the same. According to UNESCO, high-income countries' digital education offerings covered 80% of the population, and in low-income countries only 50% of the student population received digital education. Erratic electricity supply and limited digital literacy coupled with the lack of devices were major impediments in access to digital education in most developing and under-developed countries.

Thus, a significant third of the world population was unable to access remote learning. In India, too, unstable internet connection and low broadband penetration in semi-urban and rural areas impacted digital learning opportunities. The adoption of digital technology was smoother among private schools in India, but government schools and the bulk of lower end schools were not able to take that digital leap seamlessly. In Brazil, for instance, 95% of the children from privileged families had computers at home, while only 14% of the students from low-income families had computers at home. In the USA, 100% of students from affluent families had computers at home, while only 25% from poor families did.

With the long gap in learning, coupled with differential access, unreliable assessment standards and inadequate checks and balance, the students are

inevitably facing major learning gaps. In the UK, there was evidence of an increased 'word gap' among students at the transition from primary to secondary school. The Ofsted November 2020 report on the situation before the second UK lockdown highlighted that the primary school children have experienced losses across a range of subjects or were at the same level as March 2020. Vast deficits were also evident in social and communication skill, listening skills, speech, phonics and motor skills. Some students could not even hold a pencil!

A study by Azim Premji Foundation highlighted that 82% of children across 5 Indian States have lost at least one specific mathematical ability, such as identifying numbers, performing operations or problem solving, when compared to last year. Similarly, 92% of children, on an average, have lost at least one specific language ability such as oral expression, reading fluency, writing skill and reading comprehension, compared to the previous year. This is seen uniformly across all classes.

The inequity in access has also translated to disparities in learning. Students from disadvantaged groups not only struggled to gain access to remote learning but also had to struggle with achieving the desired learning outcomes. In the USA, the white students were only 1 to 3 months behind in their learning schedule, while the students of colour were 3 to 5 months behind in their learning. A survey by ChildFund in 20 backward districts across 10 States in India revealed that 64% of students in rural areas felt that they would have to drop out of school if not given additional support. While the specific data for deficits observed in learning outcomes for the marginalised groups in India is still not available, circumstantial evidence suggests that the digital divide and socio-economic backwardness may have severely impacted education for this group.

Apart from learning outcomes, an oft-ignored aspect in the Indian education ecosystem is mental health. With the highest rate of student suicide rates in the world, India can no longer ignore this aspect, especially with the closure of schools. The ChildFund Survey reported that a majority of the parents observed an increase in adverse behaviour in their wards, and more than 60 per cent of children themselves felt behavioural changes such as increased anger, irritability and lack of concentration. Mental health will assume an important dimension once children return to schools and deal with anxiety and separation. The emotional well-being of those cramped in small homes

with no contact from their classmates and teachers needs to be particularly looked into.

Moreover, the complete disappearance of Early Childhood Care and Education in the COVID years will have large scale ramifications for the social, emotional, cognitive and physical needs of children and thereby impact learning outcomes for a vast majority in the future. The inequities in access to education will most likely translate into long term income losses and the decline in a skilled workforce. It will also impact intergenerational mobility, with disadvantaged groups having even fewer educational opportunities than normal years.

HAS COVID-19 IMPACTED ACCESS TO EDUCATION?

The year 2020 is a tragic one for a variety of reasons. One of those is by way of its impact on education and on schooling. Enrolment rates in 2020 are relatively lower than those in 2018. While children between ages 6-7 are possibly waiting for schools to reopen to seek admission, a worrying trend is a drop in enrolment among children aged 15-16. The Annual Status of Education Report (ASER) 2020 by Pratham highlights how the pandemic is impacting schools and learning outcomes in Rural India. The survey answers some troubling concerns about the school system in the post-COVID world.

PANDEMIC IMPACT ON ENROLMENT

As one would expect with the ongoing crisis, the survey indicates that a vast majority of such children perhaps are probably compelled to find remunerative jobs to ease their families' distress. The enrolment patterns are also witnessing a significant turnaround. A shift is observed in enrolment, from private schools to government schools between 2018 and 2020. The increased enrolment in government schools is particularly apparent among both boys and girls in secondary schools. This could be attributed mainly to the inability of parents to furnish financial burdens of private schooling as well as the closure of several private schools, given the economic crunch post the stringent lockdown. The dip in enrolments is not restricted to India. In the USA, for instance, Washington's public-school enrolment fell by 3% since the last academic cycle. The enrolment decline was significant across all levels of schooling and all districts in the state. A move towards home-schooling or private education is being reported among parents in the USA.

DOES THE PANDEMIC IMPACT INTERGENERATIONAL MOBILITY?

Parental education is an indicator of socio-economic status for households. It also means access to smartphones and the internet as well as the choice of schools. The survey highlights that parents with lower education levels (both parents have Std V or fewer years of schooling) send their children to government schools, whereas those with higher education (Both have Std IX or more) educate their

Has Covid-19 Impacted access to Education?

Children in private schools. The ASER report also points out that as parents' education and income levels rise, enrolment in government schools goes

down. Moreover, about 40% of students from households with lower parentaleducation did not do any activity (online classes or traditional learning).

Among families where parents have higher levels of education, the availability of smartphones is also higher than when compared to households with low parental education. 90% of children in homes with adequately educated parents received family support for learning, while only 50% of those in lower education households received such support. The pandemic has reaffirmed that the socio-economic status of households is a factor determining the opportunities available to young children. Children from educationally and poor families will have to battle the odds of not having amenities like smartphone, internet, electricity as well as counter the absence of learning assistance at home.

HOW COMMUNITY CAN SUPPORT AID TEACHING AND LEARNING?

Community engagement and support have assumed prime importance in times of remote learning. While physical interaction among teachers and students is absent, other stakeholders must take responsibility to ensure learning and service delivery is as seamless as possible. ASER states that in rural India, about 70% schools got help from community members in reaching children. The survey observed that among parents with low education levels, children receive assistance from elder siblings. In households with higher parental education, 45% of the children received aid from their mothers. ASER highlights that parents with higher education levels seemed to have established significant contact with schoolteachers and in turn, receive support from schools. Approximately 34% of all children's teachers in rural areas contacted parents or families to discuss learning material and child's progress. The states of Bihar, Tripura and Punjab report the highest percentage of school respondents who take help from village/ community members to support children's learning. While in the state of Kerala, local volunteers and NGOs were proactive in supporting schools, in Rajasthan Anganwadi workers actively support learning opportunities.

HAS ONLINE EDUCATION EXACERBATED THE DIGITAL DIVIDE?

The survey notes that 43.6% of children in government schools do not have access to a smartphone, while among those in private schools a relatively lower proportion (25%) of students did not have access to a smartphone. Even with the lack of traditional classroom teaching, 60% of children stuck to

textbooks in both government and private schools. About 47% of private school children reported using recorded video lessons and live classes as opposed to 26% of government school children. WhatsApp was the most popular medium for the dissemination learning materials and activities.

A higher proportion of students enrolled in private schools received materials through WhatsApp than their counterparts in government schools. Children in government schools received materials and activities through phone calls or personal visits. Possibly, a result of lower smartphone availability among government school children. However, it is observed that for all grades, the availability of textbooks among government school children is much higher than their private school counterparts. While online education has deepened the divide between the haves and have-nots, family and community support have grown to plug in the gaps.

Once the schools reopen, significant efforts shall be needed to make up for the learning losses as well as to reintegrate students into traditional schooling systems. However, the crisis has brought out mechanisms to ensure a smooth transition from the digital to the physical world. As ASER data points out, more than 75% of fathers and mothers have more than primary school education. Given that parents are now more educated than ever before, they should be used in school systems as mediators in bridging educational inadequacies. With the New Education Policy on the cards, a lot can be done to explore strategies to combine e-learning and traditional education to increase the robustness of school systems. It is essential to keep the community support constant even after the pandemic, to ensure all stakeholders are actively involved in the well-being and progress.

IMPACT OF COVID-19 ON EDUCATION

- Across 188 countries, 90 per cent of the countries adopted digital and/or broadcast remote learning policies.
- Only 60 per cent of countries imparted remote learning at the pre-primary level.
- 31 % or 463 million children worldwide could not avail online education due to the lack of access to digital technology and infrastructure.
- 3 out of 4 students globally who could not access schools online, belonged either to rural areas or to the poorest households or both.

Source: UNICEF

0 - Closed due to COVID-19 | 1 - Partially Open | 2 - Academic Break | 3 - Fully Open

Timeline of school closure in India

Source: Lok Sabha Unstarred Question

STATUS OF SCHOOL IN INDIA

Source: UNICEF

Schools were completely closed in India late March 2020. Most schools remained shut till mid-January 2021. However, in several parts of India, schools were opened partially in October 2020.

SCHOOL CLOSURES ACROSS THE WORLD

- Number of Students in countries with fully closed schools 719,436,660
- Number of Students in countries with partially closed schools 111,632,094

STATUS OF SCHOOLS ACROSS THE WORLD

- 0- Closed due to COVID-19
- 1- Open with limitation
- 2- Open

Among Low-Income Countries, while the number of students enrolled in schools is high, the schools in these countries remained closed or partially open due to COVID19. This is particularly significant for countries like Ethiopia, Congo, Afghanistan and Tanzania, where many students will be affected due to school closures-thereby impacting students and learning outcomes.

In Lower Middle-Income Countries, the graph indicates a greater number of countries opted for complete closure of schools. In these countries, the population of students enrolled in schools is also extremely high. For instance, India which has 320,713,792 students enrolled in schools, had closed its schools, late March onwards. As did Bangladesh and Indonesia.

Among Upper-Middle Income Countries, most countries managed to keep their schools partially open during the pandemic outbreak. China kept schools open in a limited fashion to accommodate its reasonably large student population. Brazil followed a similar trend.

Among high-income countries, fewer countries closed their schools completely. United Kingdom, Germany and Italy opted for complete closure despite a significant student population. The U.S, Japan and France, also comprising a large student population, continued to operate their schools with restrictions.

HOW INCLUSIVE ARE PRIVATE SCHOOLS?

Private school education has undergone a paradigm shift in terms of its structure, demographics, economics as well as learning mechanisms. Private unaided schools have become affordable and accessible to a large proportion of the Indian population. While a colonial hangover has left Indians enamoured with the idea of English-medium education, the sharp reduction in the cost of private education has attracted parents from varied income and social groups, into its folds. However, while the diversity in private schooling is now vibrant, the integration of this admixture should be less about assimilation and more about development around its distinctiveness.

As per the State of the Sector Report: Private Schools in India, the growth of enrolment in private unaided schools increased to 34.8% in 2017 from 9.2% in 1993. During the same period, the growth of enrolment in government schools has declined from 70.8% to 52.2%. A massive shift has thus been observed among all income groups towards private schools. According to Unified District Information on School Education (U-DISE) 2019, private unaided schools cater to 9 crore students in the country. Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation (MoSPI) 2019 pegged the contribution of this sector at ₹ 1.75 lakh crore. With about 45.5% of students paying a monthly fee of less than ₹ 500, private education no longer remains the exclusive privilege of the rich.

Incentives such as vouchers and direct cash transfers to mothers, private-public partnerships, subsidisation of private schools and hybrid models such as the RTE Act Section 12 (1)(c) have significantly boosted private school participation. The section 12 (1)(c) of the RTI Act obligates private unaided schools to reserve 25% of their seats at the entry-level for children from economically and socially disadvantaged groups.

However, inequalities in wealth, caste, religion, and gender permeate the very structure of private education in India. About 54% of the richest families access private education, while only 12% of the poorest families avail of the same. Interestingly, approximately 38% of students in private schools come

From the poorest 60% population. Additionally, the affordability of private schooling is impacted by poverty and family size. The greater the number of children in a family, the more constraints on the amount that can be spent on each child.

Disparities in school education exist with regard to caste as well. As much as 67% of those from the forward castes make use of private unaided schools and only 20.7% of the same group study at government schools. Students from scheduled castes (SC) and scheduled tribes (ST) in private unaided schools comprise only 24.9% and 17.2% respectively. A higher proportion of SC and ST students – 64.8% and 72.5% respectively attend government schools. A majority of the students from other backward castes (OBC) receive education in government schools, while 35% of the students have access to private schooling. SC students thus have lowest enrolment in private schools.

The participation of boys and girls in private unaided schools is also slightly skewed. As much as 38% of boys are enrolled in private unaided schools, while this figure for girls is at 31.5%. In comparison, female students enrolled comprise 55.7% in government schools, while boys make up 49.5%. NSSO data for the 75th round highlights the average expenditure on education for females, which is 11-18% lower than that of males.

Religious communities, too, exhibit an unequal distribution of participation in private unaided schools. Hindu, Muslims, and Christians each have about 25% of their students attending private schools. Sikhs have about 40% of students enrolled in private schools. Economically better off communities such as Jains and Parsis have about 63% and 88% of their student population accessing private schooling. In government schools, the highest enrolment (69%) of students is from the Buddhist community. Equal participation of students in government schools comes from Hindus and Muslims of about 63%. Christian and Sikh students comprise 50% and 45% approximately. Only 20% of students from the Jain community attend government schools.

The disparities in education patterns will have long-term consequences on inter-generational income and educational equity. The state must ensure mechanisms that not only encourage diversity in schooling but also policies that prevent discrimination among students. Moreover, a preference for English-medium private schools will lead to absolute neglect of the mother tongue as a medium of instruction. The imposition of another language is an added disadvantage for students coming from marginalised groups. The New Education Policy of 2019 highlights the importance of teaching and learning languages in the 8th Schedule of the Constitution, while tribal languages and dialects may not be given the same significance. A representative education system must have a structure to incorporate diversity in languages as well.

MINORITIES MISSING

From what the Prime Minister has said and what was articulated at the government's press conference, the NEP-2020 is a paradigm shift in India's education. That is where it gets exciting, and immediately, that is where it stops too. Like everything 'grandiose' that these final kinks are ironed out. On paper, there are several points the policy makes in the right direction. However, it is one more nail in the coffin of decentralisation and makes a federal-state far more unitary than it ever was. Education, which ought to be a local area subject, is now firmly with the Union Government.

Let's first take up the issue of financing education. There is no set-in-stone commitment to increasing the budgetary spending to 6% of GDP from the ever-lagging actual estimated spending between '1.6% – 4.6% [26.1, 26.2 - NEP 2020, Policy Document]. With no hard-wired commitment to increasing investment in education, which has dogged the development of quality education infrastructure since independence, this policy also looks like another announcement of the present government that will go nowhere.

Drilling down into one of the most fundamental purposes of institutionalising education, 'empowering of minorities', the NEP-2020 document uses the word minorities thrice in the whole of its 62 pages. With almost non-existent detail but only a passing mention of an essential reading makes one wonder about the departure from how visible minority inclusion has been until now. Other than some fleeting references to inequalities of caste and lip service to scheduled castes, the NEP 2020 doesn't really speak about how it might accommodate the rife social-economic-cultural inequalities we have in our society.

There is hardly any elucidation on minorities other than language inclusivity in terms of education. With NEP-2020, linguistic minorities might gain access to learning in their mother tongues, which are again probably subject to the local states where education is administered according to their interpretation and implementation of the policy and making of rules. Earlier policies did do a lot of lip service on this issue too, yet not much has come out of it, the religious-minorities/tribal/indigenous persons today still feel estranged from 'state-education' that distances them from their roots. Education in Sanskrit and classical languages' non-religious literature has been emphasised, both at the school and the higher education levels.

Scholars from top tier institutions belonging to lower socio-economic backgrounds who studied in vernacular until their 12th grade were interviewed. Their common concern that transitions to English medium from education in the vernacular is tough has not been elucidated on by NEP-2020.

There is no mention in the policy, of the inclusion of education of religious minorities. And neither is there any information on religious/faith-based schooling being bridged to mainstream education. The policy also does not detail much about the functioning of religious minority institutions and how they might weave into the fabric of either schooling or higher education. How religious-minority institutions react to this is an issue to be watched out for.

The policy also lacks any mention of accommodations of minorities under reservations or affirmative action(s). A reading of the policy gives an assumption that it assumes almost there exists no inequalities of all the relevant actors in education be it students, teachers/academics and educational institutions. The policy seemingly homogenises everyone. The new overseer of higher education 'Higher Education Commission of India (HECI)' and how it might function is wide open to interpretation according to the policy.

But one thing becomes evident that there is going to be significantly more centralisation when it comes to the administration of education. Content and quality of schooling are also going to be overseen centrally even if it is administered by the states. The immediate fall out of such centralisation is that the only debate about the NEP that rages in the country is on the language formula. What a school uses to teach its students who come from the immediate neighbourhood is best left for the school to decide.

This is what will allow a Gujarati medium school to co-exist with a Marathi medium school in Hyderabad, a city where Telugu and Urdu medium schools abound. School education is best administered when the local community and the elected politicians are responsible for delivery in the public sector. Higher education policy can be discussed at the centre but even their Universities are best left autonomous to decide what kind of entry requirements and evaluation they would have in place.

Finally, a policy that talks about increasing the Gross enrolment ratio in colleges and universities must also lay a strong emphasis on the need to bring all vulnerable communities, their children and particularly they get enrolled

and stay in the formal education setup for at least 16 years. Else we will continue to have a situation where the mean years of schooling for an average Indian is just 6.5, less than half of what we see in Europe.

The Indian Muslim child stays on average in school for less than five years. The New Policy, far from increasing access to education, might just make it more difficult for the poor to attend secondary school and almost impossible to go to University. We need a strong push to improve the level of education infrastructure in the country by way of better schools, improved connectivity, better-trained teachers, and a strong institutional mechanism that allows students to be graded and evaluated holistically without making examinations the end-all of the education system.

STATE OF HIGHER EDUCATION IN INDIA: CHALLENGES & WAY FORWARD

ABSTRACT

While primary education has received focused attention from successive Indian governments over the years, the higher education sector in the country has remained largely neglected. This is despite higher education providing skills and training that help sustain growth, innovate on technology, and reduce poverty. India's higher education sector is transforming to meet unprecedented levels of demand arising from economic, social, technological and demographic changes. This paper seeks to provide a detailed analysis of the state of higher education in India, the policy processes governing it, and the challenges faced by the sector. It also seeks to explore issues concerning access to higher education and quality of education imparted as well. To this end, the paper discusses the National Education Policy 2020 as well as the impact it can have on higher education in the country.

INTRODUCTION

Like several other developing nations, India has conventionally neglected higher education over the years to focus its efforts on primary education that provides the 'Three Rupees' – reading, writing and arithmetic. Crucial for the labour market and the country's development, higher education helps sustain growth, brings in innovation, and keeps families out of poverty by imparting knowledge and skills necessary for jobs that offer good wages and living conditions (Tilak, 2012). Higher education helps consolidate the knowledge received through primary and secondary education, while ensuring that people who escape the trap of poverty – educational as well as income poverty – do not fall back into it.

Higher education in India is on a path of major transformation as the sector seeks to meet high levels of demand that arise from fast-paced economic, demographic, technological and industry-led changes. As India seeks to reap the benefits of its demographic dividend, provision of quality education for all is a challenge faced by both the central and state governments. Several

private educational institutions have come up in the past three decades and the number of students attending college or university has steadily increased (UKIBC, 2018).

India is expected to have the largest college-going population of 140 million students in the world by 2030, creating a need for 1,500 more institutions to accommodate this huge influx. There are 1,043 universities, 42,343 colleges and 11,779 stand-alone institutions in India for higher education, as per the All India Survey on Higher Education 2019-20 (Government of India, 2020a). Total enrolment in higher education stands at 38.5 million, with 19.6 million males and 18.9 million females. Women constitute about 49%.

The country's gross enrolment ratio (GER) is 27.1% (around 27 of 100 eligible students attend higher educational institutions), calculated for the 18-23 age group. GER was 25.2% in 2016-17, 24.3% in 2014-15 and 19.4% in 2010-11 (Nanda, 2018b). It was 26.3% in 2018-19. One of the National Education Policy 2020's objectives is for India to attain 50% GER in higher education by 2035 through capacity expansion and restructuring in existing institutes (Government of India, 2020b). While national GER has improved steadily over the years, more educated people will need jobs in a country witnessing its highest unemployment rates in decades. GER varies significantly among all the states. Sikkim leads with a GER of 75%, followed by Tamil Nadu and Chandigarh at 51% and 52%, respectively. Unemployment rates were at 7.8% in February 2020 (Trading Economics, 2020).

SNAPSHOT OF INDIA'S HIGHER EDUCATION SECTOR

India currently has 1,043 universities, 39,931 colleges and 10,725 standalone institutions.

- GER increased from 24.5% in 2015-16 to 25.2% in 2016-17. It stands at 26.3% as of 2018-19, and 27.1% in 2019-20.
- Enrolment in HEIs increased from 32 million in 2013-14 to 38.5 million in 2018-19. Females constitute 49% of the total enrolment.
- 140 million Indians will be in college-going age group – largest in world by 2030, requiring 1,500 more institutions to accommodate influx. Of the 1 million people who enter the labour market every month, less than 25% are considered employable.

- Student-to-teacher ratio increased from a low of 24 in 2013-14 to a high of 29 in 2017-18, and 28 in 2019-20.
- 35% of teaching positions at various central universities under the purview of UGC are lying vacant.

There are eight levels of higher education offered: PhD, M.Phil., post-graduate, undergraduate, PG diploma, diploma, certificate, and integrated. Comprising about 80% of the total enrolment, the highest number of students are enrolled in the undergraduate level. This is followed by 11% of those pursuing their post-graduation, 6.9% of those doing diploma courses, and about 1% in integrated PhD and PhD programmes. Approximately 1% of those enrolled are in a certificate and PG diploma levels. This suggests that as we move towards higher levels of education, enrolment levels drop considerably (Government of India, 2020a).

Students from the scheduled castes constitute 14.7%, and scheduled tribes make up 5.6% of the total enrolment. As many as 37% of students belong to other backward classes. Though Muslims constitute about 14% of the country's population, students comprise only 5.5% of total enrolment. Students from other minority communities make up 2.3% (Government of India, 2020a) of the total enrolment.

The number of universities and other similar institutions listed through AISHE has risen from 760 in 2014-15 to 1,043 in 2019-20, by almost 37%. The number of colleges has increased from 38,498 in 2014-15 to 42,343 in 2019-20, by about 10%. Kerala has the highest age-specific attendance ratio (ASAR) in the 18-23 years age group, among all states at 47%, compared to a national average of 28.8%. ASAR is the proportion of children/adults of a particular age group attending school or college, irrespective of their level of study. The 18-23 age group comprises those pursuing higher education (Government of India, 2021).

The central and state government's expenditure on education has been around 3% of GDP between 2014-15 and 2018-19, the Economic Survey 2019-20 notes. National Education Policy 2020 reaffirms India's commitment to increase this to 6% of GDP. About 41% of the total allocation to the Ministry of Education for 2021-22 is for the Department of Higher Education. Accounting for a 2% rise over 2019-20, this amounts to ₹ 38,351

crore. In 2020-21, the department was allocated ₹ 39,467 crore in the budget. In revised estimates, this was reduced by about 17% to ₹ 32,900 crore. Under all major expense heads, grants to central universities and IITs constitute the largest share in the 2021-22 allocation to the higher education department at about 20% each. While about ₹ 7,686 crore has been allocated to IITs, grants to central universities amount to ₹ 7,643 crore in 2021-22. (Kumar, 2021).

Figure: Allocation for higher education over the past decade (in crore).

Source: (PRS Legislative Research, 2021)

Figure: Budget Estimates for 2021-22 under Major Expense Heads (In Crore).

Source: (PRS Legislative Research, 2021)

BACKGROUND & CONTEXT

Higher education institutes in India have registered an increase in their enrolment from 32 million in 2013-14 to nearly 38.5 million in 2019-20. Uttar Pradesh has the highest student enrolment, followed by Maharashtra and Tamil Nadu. While the increase in GER has been encouraging, questions have been raised about the quality of education being imparted and students' employability after graduation. Besides this, the growing student population and decreasing number of teachers also suggest understaffing in higher education.

Several reasons are attributed to the shortage of faculty in higher education institutions. Teaching has become a less-preferred profession due to lower pay than other jobs and a lack of research and career growth opportunities. With most open faculty positions being contractual, graduates seem to value the job security and monetary benefits they receive in other jobs. One of the criteria for appointment/promotions in teaching to the professor/associate professor level is a doctoral degree in the concerned discipline. The number of students pursuing their PhD has registered an increase from 0.1 million in 2013-14 to nearly 0.2 million in 2019-20. This will help ensure a better supply of qualified teaching staff. As many as 38,886 students were awarded PhDs in 2019-20, 21,577 males and 17,409 were females. As per the AISHE report for 2019-20, 2,02,550 students were enrolled in PhD programmes.

Pupil-Teacher Ratio (PTR) in universities and colleges is 28 in 2019-20 compared to 29 in 2018-19, if regular mode enrolment is considered. PTR for universities and their constituent units is 18 for regular mode. PTR is more than 50 in Bihar and Jharkhand. In regular mode, Daman & Diu has the best TPR of 14 in universities and colleges. Puducherry, Goa, Andhra Pradesh, Kerala, Karnataka and Tamil Nadu have a TPR below 20 (Government of India, 2020a). According to the 2018 Parliamentary Standing Committee Report on Human Resource Development, Demand for Grants 2018-19 of the Department of Higher Education, approximately 36% of teaching positions at various central universities under the purview of UGC (University Grants Commission) were lying vacant (1,323 professors, 2,217 associate professors, 2,457 assistant professors). As of September 2020, 6,210 teaching posts across 42 central universities were unfilled (Kumar, 2021).

Despite solid growth in enrolment, India's participation in higher education is still low when compared to China (26%), Brazil (36%) and the UK

(nearly 50%). The Times Higher Education (THE) World University Ranking, 2020, sees no Indian university in the list of top 300 universities, a first since 2012. Indian Institute of Science, Bangalore, which was in the 251-300 rank bracket last year, dropped 50 spots and was in the 301-350 cohort in 2020. The rankings fell due to a decline in research citation impact score, the existing teaching environment, and income levels in the sector ("World University Rankings", 2019). In comparison, seven Chinese universities have made it to the top 200, and China's Tsinghua University (Rank 23) is the highest-ranked university in Asia.

HIGHER EDUCATION IN INDIA AND OTHER COUNTRIES

The growing GER

Establishing small, high-quality institutions was in stark contrast to what China, the United States and European countries followed. In China, for instance, 41.8 million students were enrolled in just 2,596 Higher Educational Institutions (HEIs) in 2016. Having students concentrated in a relatively small number of institutions allowed these countries to scale up faster and manage the higher education system more easily.

The growth of India's higher education sector since 2001 is comparable to most other developing countries. But few countries have expanded on the same scale. From 2001 to 2016, India added 26.9 million students to its higher education system. One country that has far outpaced India is China. Between 1996 and 2001, both countries had similar GERs. However, China almost doubled its enrolment rate from 9.76% to 20% in the next few years, while India's enrollment increased by less than 2%. More importantly, China is close to achieving universalised higher education within 15 years of entering the mass stage of development (British Council India, 2014). The drastic increase in China's GER is due to increased higher education funding in the last two decades. Besides, it is easier to achieve scale in China as the students are concentrated in fewer universities. For instance, Indian HEIs, on average, have about 690 students. Chinese HEIs, on the other hand, have 16,000 students per HEI.

The growth of higher education institutions and enrolment has continued in the last five years, with over 6,000 institutions and six million students being added to the higher education system from 2011-2012 to 2016-2017. Under the Rashtriya Uchchatar Shiksha Abhiyan 2.0 (RUSA) the Ministry of

Human Resource Development has set a target of achieving 32% GER by 2022. Going by the current growth rates, this target is likely to be met in the next few years. However, India is not the only country to experience such dramatic growth (Brookings India, 2019)

Why Is the Indian GER Lower than the others?

In India, successful completion of the 12th grade in secondary school grants basic eligibility for enrollment in higher education. The relatively low GER in higher education in India is primarily due to a shortage of eligible candidates. This shortage is mainly the result of low enrollments and high dropout rates at the school level. Several factors such as gender, the language of instruction, and socioeconomic constraints are responsible for the gradual decreasing trend of the number of students during secondary school. This shortage of eligible candidates represents a major bottleneck hindering an increase of the GER in higher education (Mittal & Patwardhan, 2020).

Comparing GER and EER

Measuring Access to Higher Education in India (Mittal & Patwardhan, 2020) studied data collected over five years (2013–2017) by the UNESCO Institute for Statistics. The missing data for the completion rate was calculated using a forecasting tool incorporating a linear regression model. The eligible enrollment ratio EER obtained for the ten selected countries was compared with their respective gross enrollment ratio GER. It was discovered that the absolute difference between the EER values of higher-income countries and those of lower-middle-income countries was much smaller than the respective differences in GER values. Interestingly, it was also noticed that while the GER and EER were both consistently high for higher-income countries such as the United States (GER 88.2 per cent, EER 93.5 per cent), France (65.6 per cent, 75.5 per cent) and the United Kingdom (60.0 per cent, 63.1 per cent), the difference between GER and EER for these same countries was less than ten percentage points, which is an indication of relatively stable and mature education systems.

Their study showed that India (EER 64.3 per cent) offers better access to higher education than the United Kingdom (EER 63.1 per cent). The GER of Indonesia (36.4 per cent) is higher than in India however its EER (57.7 per cent) is lower. Pakistan ranks last among the selected countries both in terms of GER (9.4 per cent) and EER (43.3 per cent). India ranks eighth in terms of

GER but ranks sixth when using the EER as an indicator. A large difference between GER and EER indicates a large gap between the age group and eligible population.

The study further went on to show that in 2017, the difference between GER and EER in India was 37.5, the highest among all selected countries. This is an indication of the poor state of the school system, aggravated by a low rate of access to higher education. For a country like India, the EER offers a more realistic estimation: Considering educational eligibility and age gives better precision when measuring the level of participation in higher education. The hallmark of policy for any country is the quality of its higher education. Higher-income countries like Australia, the United Kingdom, and the United States can effectively participate in the knowledge economy thanks to their high-quality education focusing on skills acquisition and concern for employability.

These countries also attract a huge number of international students, which boosts enrollments. In addition, with the current trend of using continuing education coupled with rapid changes in technology and job markets, the working population above 23 makes up an increasing share of enrollments. Therefore, the definition of the GER, which is linked to a specific age group, needs to be reconsidered.

Figure: Country-wise participation in higher education (in %).

Source: (UKIBC, 2017)

PRESENT CHALLENGES

Most of the challenges facing India's higher education sector stem from a shortage of qualified teaching staff, poor quality of education imparted, absence of accountability mechanisms and separation of research, teaching and vocational skills training. In the absence of sufficient engagement between the industry and academia, the perception that vocational skills and training are inferior to other academic fields has affected employability among graduates. Several social and geographical barriers exist in ensuring equal access to all. (UKIBC, 2017).

Less than half of India's graduates are considered employable, as per the India Skills Report, 2021. Only about 46% of all graduates were found to be employable, a trend that has been on the decline in recent years. While women (41%) are considered more employable than men (34%), the workforce participation rate shows that 64% of the workforce comprises men instead of 36% women. Moreover, controversies have been erupting across universities in the country with regard to academic freedom. While the previous regimes were guilty of trying to curb the autonomy of universities, the current ruling dispensation has repeatedly attacked the freedom of speech and expression on campuses (EPW, 2018).

The gender divide in the uptake of professional courses is evident. There is lower female participation in these courses when compared to academic studies at both undergraduate and post-graduate levels. The gap is higher in enrolment in professional courses in private institutions. However, data also shows that gender parity in higher education is improving. In 2015-16, for every 100 male students, there were 86 female students. This increased to 92 female students for every 100 male students in 2019-20. 17 universities are exclusively for women in India, as per the AISHE 2019-20.

While the national gross enrolment ratio (GER) is 26.3%, the GER for the male population is 26.9%, and for females, it is 27.3% (Government of India, 2020a). Total enrolment in higher education is 38.5 million, with 19.6 million male and 18.9 female students. A cursory glance at the male-female ratio at each level shows that males' ratio is higher than females at almost every level, except M.Phil, Post Graduate and Certificate courses.

Figure: Gender Distribution at Various Levels of Higher Education.
 Source: AISHE (2019-20)

This is reflected across most states as well. Uttar Pradesh, Maharashtra, Tamil Nadu, Rajasthan, Madhya Pradesh and Karnataka are the six leading states in total student enrolment, comprising about 53.8% of India's total student enrolment. Almost 53.7% of the total female students enrolled come from these six states, and the states' male students comprise about 54% of the total male students across India (Government of India, 2020a).

Figure: Top 6 states as per enrolment and representation of male and female students.
 Source: AISHE 2019-20

Figure: Percentage distribution of enrolment among various categories.

Source: AISHE 2018-19

Scheduled caste (SC) students constitute 14.7%, and scheduled tribe (ST) students make up 5.6% of the enrolled students. As many as 37% of students belong to other backward classes (OBC) and 42.7% to the 'general' category. While 5.4% of students belong to the Muslim community, 2.3% belong to other minority communities.

Figure: Percentage enrolment of Muslims and other minorities over the years

Source: AISHE 2019-20

In the recent past, scholarships for underprivileged students were being delayed, leading to an increase in the number of college dropouts (Sundar, 2018). A delay in receiving his scholarship was one of the reasons attributed to Dalit student Rohit Vemula's suicide at the Central University in Hyderabad in 2016, an incident that led to nationwide campus protests and sparked renewed debates about caste discrimination in Indian colleges and universities.

Since 1943 and introduced by BR Ambedkar, the Post-matriculation Scholarship Scheme for Scheduled Caste Students (PMS-SC) is a centrally-sponsored programme aimed at providing financial assistance through state and UT administrations to students from marginalised communities for post-matriculation education. Until 2018, the government and states shared the responsibility of funding the scheme in a 60:40 ratio under a 'committed liability' formula. By the end of the 12th five year plan, this came down to almost 10:90 and the scheme nearly shut down in 14 states (Trivedi, 2020).

In March 2018, the central government said it could owe states about ₹ 8,600 crore in unpaid scholarship claims from SC students. Out of a total ₹ 11,027.5 crore sought by the Department of Social Justice and Empowerment, only ₹ 7,750 crore was received as outlay. This affected PMS-SC the most, the Department of Social Justice and Empowerment had said (Chowdhury, 2018). In December 2020, the government announced a new funding plan with a total investment of ₹ 59,048 crore for the next five years. Of this, the central government would spend ₹ 35,534 crore or roughly about 60%. The 'fixed sharing' pattern replaces the existing 'committed liability' system and ensures greater involvement from the central government (Cabinet Committee on Economic Affairs, 2020). Through this, the government aims to bring in 1.36 crore students from 'poorest of poor' families into a higher education course of their choice, who would have otherwise dropped out after Class 10. A report of the Standing Committee on Social Justice and Empowerment (2021) states that only about 113 lakh students have benefitted from the scheme in the past two years (2018-19 and 2019-20). At least 80 lakh beneficiaries must be covered annually to achieve the target of 4 crore students in the next five years, the report noted.

India's policy for improving access to higher education has typically centred around affirmative action through quota-based reservation for different social groups. This is based on the premise that participation of people from

reserved categories has been low and quota-based reservation will help tackle this (Basant and Sen, 2010). SC/ST candidates had been the primary focus of this policy until 1990 with all other castes being grouped under the 'other categories'. This changed when OBCs were recognised as a separate category for affirmative action following the Mandal Commission's 1980 report that called for 27% reservation for OBCs in central government jobs and central university education.

Reservation for OBCs in central government jobs was implemented in 1992 itself. However, the Central Educational Institutions and (Reservations in Admissions) Amendment Bill was passed only in 2006, implementing 27% reservation for OBCs in central universities. Soon after, protests erupted all across the country against the policy and the Supreme Court stayed the implementation of the Act following a public interest litigation. In 2008, the Supreme Court upheld the OBC quota of 27%, while introducing a 'creamy layer' criterion for such positive discrimination. All central educational institutions were also instructed to expand their capacity such that the total number of seats available to students who belonged to the 'general' category remained the same. Currently, 15% is reserved for SC and 7.5% for ST candidates. Several states had their own reservation policies for higher education before the bill was passed and continued it even after.

One of the major challenges in implementing caste-based reservation in India is the difference between central and state lists of OBCs. A parliamentary committee on the welfare of OBCs said that only about 21% of the 27% reserved for OBCs in government jobs had been filled up in 2016 (Ministry of Social Empowerment and Justice, 2019). Moreover, a 2017 commission headed by retired Delhi High Court Chief Justice G. Rohini constituted to look into the sub-categorisation of OBCs said that out of about 6,000 castes and communities that come under the OBC category, 40 communities accounted for about 50% of all reservation claimed under the quota for civil service jobs and education in central universities. As much as 20% were excluded from any kind of reservation in 2014-18.

Several studies have combined caste and community categories to assess the impact of affirmative action. The Sachar Committee Report on the conditions of Muslims in India (Government of India, 2006) took the socio-religious categories of Hindus (general category, SC, ST and OBC), Muslims (general and OBC), and other minorities. The analysis of these SRCs that were further

divided into poor and non-poor based on economic considerations showed educational and employment conditions varied across the SRCs.

Basant and Sen looked into the impact of affirmative action on the participation of OBCs in higher education (2016). Their study points out that it may be misleading to go just by deficits in participation in higher education by looking at the share of currently enrolled persons in higher education courses in the relevant age cohort of a social group. If one does not complete school, one will not be eligible for higher education. The link between school education and higher education will be brought into focus by considering the eligible population (those who have completed secondary education) in each group. Basant and Sen (2014) also argue in favour of parental education as a criterion for affirmative action instead of socio-religious affiliations. The authors raise questions over a generalised nationwide policy for reservation while there are large regional variations among different social groups in participation. They also call for encouraging participation in higher education through capacity expansion in higher educational institutions and primary and secondary schools.

PRIVATISATION OF HIGHER EDUCATION

Among 1,043 universities, 396 universities are privately managed. Majority of the colleges (78.6%) in India are privately managed, of which 65.2% are private unaided and 13.4% are private-aided colleges. The remaining 22.2% are government colleges (Government of India, 2020a). Private-unaided colleges in Andhra Pradesh and Telangana constitute about 80% of all colleges AISHE (2019-20). Though about 79% of all colleges are private, these colleges cater to only 66% of the total enrolment.

Figure: Management-wise Distribution of Colleges.

Source: AISHE (2019-20)

Figure: Percentage enrolment in private and government colleges.

Source: All India Survey on Higher Education (2019-20)

Widespread *laissez-faireism* in the early 1990s in higher education (Tilak 2014) resulted in the growth of private higher education. This period was followed by clear approaches that favoured private players. However, confusion remained as to whether privatisation was good or bad. There was no clear policy on it and the government was often found contradicting itself on the same. For example, while the government said privatisation was good, it also deemed the commercialisation of higher education as bad. In reality, it is accepted that profit maximisation and privatisation go hand in hand (Tilak, 2012). In this context, some courts announced that while making 'surplus' was acceptable, profits in private higher educational institutions was not. However, the difference between 'surplus' and 'profit' was not clarified.

Compelled by these policies of the World Bank and the IMF in the 1990s, and the emergence of strong markets and an Indian corporate sector, the country begrudgingly accepted privatisation as a tool for the development of higher education. India is now past that phase and formulates policies with the conviction that privatisation has a positive impact. A client-oriented higher-education system controlled by powerful societal groups required the Indian state to ensure continued patronage flows to these groups during economic reform. In the face of the Indian state's retreat from sectors such as higher education, the politics of patronage performed the function of co-opting groups, which could potentially thwart the move towards reform.

The capitation fee system was an arena where the new politics of reform was played out. An arena defined by the nexus of caste, education and politics, pre-existing patronage networks made it ideal ground for unfolding of this new politics (Krishnan, 2014).

It is important to note that unlike corporate entities, the best institutions of higher education are public institutions or private institutions that are guided by the principles of philanthropy. For-profit institutions are hardly inclusive in providing access to higher education. Recent policy reforms mark a transition in the history of higher education from a system embedded in welfare state-ism to a system partially based on quasi-market principles and finally to a system based on a neo-liberal market philosophy (Tilak, 2012).

POLICY LANDSCAPE: EVOLUTION & CHALLENGES

While the Sarkar Committee in 1948 highlighted the role technical education can play in industrialisation as it recommended the creation of IITs along the lines of the Massachusetts Institute of Technology, the Radhakrishnan Commission wanted to free higher education of the liberal arts bias it had under colonial rule. Under Prime Minister Jawaharlal Nehru, higher education and scientific education received renewed focus as they were seen as critical for socioeconomic growth and economic self-sufficiency (Krishnan, 2016). The separation between technical and other higher education was later reinforced with National Education Policy 1986. Over the years, technical education started aligning more with the needs of developed economies as graduates sought to work in the IT services industry or moved abroad.

Sectors such as manufacturing and public works failed to meet its employment needs as unemployable graduates from sub-par technical institutes aspired to join the IT-enabled sector (ITES). ITES accounts for nearly a quarter of India's organised private sector workforce. Krishnan (2016) partly attributes the gap in how India's youth understand its problems to the format of engineering in the country.

Primary education took centre-stage in the national government's education policy soon after the 1990 Education for All conference in Thailand. While this resulted in the passing of the Right of Children to Free and Compulsory Education, 2009, it also translated into a cap on the expansion of secondary and higher education until elementary educations were achieved

(Tilak, 2012). A slew of economic reforms introduced in the 1990s led to the rapid growth of private engineering colleges in number in India (Krishnan, 2014). Since these private colleges accepted huge capitation fees, their proliferation came at the cost of government engineering colleges. The two decades that followed saw ineffective policymaking in the higher education sector. Government expenditure on higher education declined in the Eighth (1992-97) and Ninth (1997-2002) Five Year Plans, and faculty recruitment and quality of education both suffered for almost a decade.

The IT boom of the 1990s led to a perception of meritocracy that promised to provide more class mobility to the aspiring middle classes. Options for stable and profitable employment were no longer limited to the public sector. However, employment in the IT sector was often the result of a combination of skill and social capital derived from caste and class identities (Upadhy and Vasavi 2006, in Krishnan, 2016). This gradually led to a situation where technical education came to be redefined as a means for socioeconomic mobility rather than a tool for nation-building.

Higher education received renewed attention in the past two decades as India prepared to transform itself into a regional power. This came with the realisation that the ability to build a 'knowledge society' and sustain economic growth cannot be developed without quality higher education (Tilak, 2012). Tilak (2012) says that a GER of 30-40% is a critical threshold to cross for India considering that developed economies with universal secondary schooling and better access to higher education have a GER of 40-90%. India targeted a GER of 15% by the end of its Eleventh Five Year Plan (2007-12) to realise the objective of inclusive growth, and achieved the target by 2009-10.

Termed an 'education plan', the 11th FYP allowed for larger funding for higher education and major expansion, under which 30 new central universities, six new IIMs, four IITs and 2,000 colleges of engineering and technology, among others were to be set up. Recruitment of faculty resumed after almost a decade's break. New scholarship schemes and subsidised student loan schemes were formulated for those from the lower socioeconomic strata (Tilak, 2012). The government also announced plans to set up 14 world class or 'innovation' universities.

National Education Policy 1986 introduced centralised regulation of higher education in India. The UGC is empowered to regulate universities teaching

general subjects in India, while the All India Council for Technical Education (AICTE) and 15 other professional councils, including Medical Council of India (MCI) and Bar Council of India, regulate medical, legal, nursing and other technical education institutions. State universities must comply with the regulations enforced by these bodies as well as the separate regulators at the state levels. Accreditation and setting of standards are carried out for relevant institutions through the National Board of Accreditation (NBA) established by AICTE, and the National Assessment and Accreditation Council (NAAC) set up by UGC.

Several committees, commissions and analysts have said that this complex regulatory mechanism has resulted in corruption and mismanagement of the higher education system, adversely affecting the quality of education imparted (Sengupta, 2018). To give quality higher education institutions complete academic and administrative autonomy, Government of India launched the Institutes of Eminence scheme in 2017. Ten public and as many private institutes were to receive support to establish themselves as world-class institutes and be freed of AICTE/UGC regulation. Government institutions would receive up to Rs 1,000 crore over five years for upgrades under the scheme (Ministry of Education, 2019). Three private universities on the list included the Jio Institute, which does not exist till date. Promoted by Reliance Industries chairman Mukesh Ambani, the decision to grant this institution the Eminence status had received widespread criticism (Sundar, 2018).

NATIONAL EDUCATION POLICY (NEP) 2020

After about 35 years since the last National Education Policy (1986) that focused on equity and access, India unveiled its new National Education Policy in 2020. Pushing for multidisciplinary and increased flexibility to focus on the talents and holistic development of students, NEP 2020 is a futuristic document in many ways. Targeting a GER of 50% in higher education by 2035, the policy envisions at least one large multidisciplinary university or college in or near every district in India by 2030. For this, 3.5 crore new seats in higher education by 2035.

The structure and length of undergraduate programmes will be adjusted to achieve multidisciplinary, allowing for multiple exit points with appropriate certification at each stage. While the four-year programme will be the

preferred format for a multidisciplinary Bachelor's degree, a student will receive a certificate upon completing one year of study, a diploma for two years and a Bachelor's degree for three years of education. Flexibility will also be allowed in Master's programmes, and vocational education will also be included in higher education programmes in a phased manner. Institutions with accreditation will be allowed to conduct online and open distance learning programmes. The new education policy reiterates the need to promote Indian languages, arts and culture as well.

NEP 2020 recommends the setting up of National Professional Standards for Teachers by 2022 to detail the qualifications and expectations from teachers at different levels of expertise. To ensure there is no redundancy, these standards will be reviewed in 2030 and every ten years, thereafter (Government of India, 2020b). The policy document calls for the establishment of a National Research Foundation that will catalyse the culture of quality research in the country's universities. A mechanism for providing graded autonomy to HEIs will also be established. Moreover, academic credits earned by a student at any HEI will be digitally stored in an Academic Bank of Credit that will be considered when the student is awarded a degree.

NEP 2020 calls for the integration of digital technology in multiple areas of education such as learning, assessment, planning, administration, and so on. To this end, the policy highlights the creation of National Educational Technology Forum (NETF) to guide central and state governments on evidence-based interventions using digital technology, and build capacities in such technology. The policy highlights the role disruptive technology such as Artificial Intelligence (AI) can play in revolutionising education. NETF will also be entrusted with identifying emerging technology and their potential and timeframe for disruption such that the education system can respond to it well in time.

Pointing out the overregulation in higher education in India, NEP 2020 recommends a complete overhaul of the same and separate functioning of the arms that undertake regulation, accreditation, funding, and setting of academic standards in higher education. Dedicating the Budget 2021-22 to the implementation of NEP 2020, the country's finance minister announced the decision to set up a Higher Education Commission of India (HECI) that will replace the existing UGC and AICTE. Outside of medical and legal

education, HECI will act as an umbrella body for the verticals of standard-setting (General Education Council), accreditation (National Accreditation Council), regulation (National Higher Education Regulatory Council), and funding (Higher Education Grants Council) of higher education institutions in India.

THE WAY FORWARD

When India's economy is growing, the education system needs to produce a skilled and educated workforce to help sustain economic growth. Higher education cannot be left to be guided by market interests alone. Besides critical thinking and skills building, it must focus on innovation and employability (Krishnan, 2016). The promise to enhance education spending to 6% of GDP has remained unfulfilled since National Education Policy 1986. While NEP 2020 is a step in the right direction, a lot more thought needs to ensure its implementation in letter and spirit in the current education scenario.

There are a few specific challenges in higher education and academic research, as identified by (Reddy, En, & Qingqing, 2016) in their study.

- **Gross Enrollment Ratio**

- The number of admissions to university degree programs has been seen to be remarkably more petite than the number of admissions to pre-university education. The Indian government aims to improve the gross enrolment ratio in higher education from 17.9% in 2012-13 to 30% by 2020 (Times of India, 2014). Hence, the current rate is low compared to 26% in China and 36% in Brazil (British Council, 2014). Several reasons explain these numbers, for example, the poor financial status of students, lack of motivation and awareness of courses among students, accessibility to the institute, scarcity of jobs after obtaining the university degree, improper guidelines in admissions criteria, a deprived system of examinations, unlawful practices in public and private institutions, and so forth. Therefore, the government must establish rigorous control measures and conduct promotional workshops not only to overcome these dichotomous problems but also to present the institutional transparency

- **Political Interference**

- Accessible literature on higher education suggests that university education is influenced by the institutional environment in a given

economy (e.g. Stensaker et al., 2014). The institutional milieu comprises a set of political, social, and regulatory behaviours (North, 1990). In their study, Xie et al. (2014) mention that China has been facing several difficulties due to political issues and scientific fraud. Similarly, political intervention is severe in the overall Indian education system (Business Standard, 2014; New Indian Express, 2015). Despite the nature of the ruling political party and elected ministers, several politicians have established their educational institutions in different segments, including secondary school, pre-university college, engineering academy, medical institute, management school, and private university. In particular, an appointment of a vice-chancellor in a state university is influenced mainly by ruling political party behaviour, including the chief minister of the respective state and the education minister. Likewise, local influential persons and leaders greatly shape faculty recruitment in a university-affiliated college. It will be even more so when faculty recruitment happens at the state and central universities. Some private universities offer faculty jobs to applicants who intend to pay bribes and based on the applicants' background (caste, community, religion, and place). In addition, many intervening issues (e.g. reservation system, fee reimbursement) need solutions for creating a high-quality academic environment first and establishing world-class universities later (Basant and Sen, 2014). This observation, however, is to be taken as a general view, but the intention is to persuade and advocate the government and other stakeholders about the current state of higher educational institutions in India.

- **Job Market Placement**

- In recent times, job market placement has become a more challenging task in higher education at both universities and affiliated institutions (Mironos et al., 2015). A recent survey by NASSCOM reports that only 25% of technical graduates and 15% of other graduates are employed in the information technology sector.³² Another survey on management discipline indicates that only 23% of graduates are employed in various corporate businesses, mainly the banking and finance sector (Times of India, 2014). According to Aspiring Minds National Employability Report, over 80% of engineering graduates are unemployable (Times of India, 2016). There is a severe and sincere

need to place emphasis on the employability aspect of education with a focus on higher education. A focus on higher university education and remuneration associated with research scholars and PhDs has been a point of contention for a while now. The quality of scholars and the dignity of these scholars have to be brought back to focus. Several reports have been made available. We have seen PhD scholars and several over qualified professionals due to the lack of opportunities line up for basic government jobs for positions of unskilled personnel such as peons. An overall revamp of the quality of scholars and opportunities available post a higher education degree is unclear in the Indian context. The skills that a student needs to be equipped with do not find their way, and the quality of skilled personnel, whether for employment or entrepreneurship, seems inadequate.

- **Inadequate Financial Support**

- In general, public higher educational institutions require ongoing financial support from the government. On top of that, the university's chief administrator is responsible for managing funding and budget allocation and controlling the misuse of such funds. In the early post-independence years, the Indian government allocated a large budget for setting up institutes of national importance, central and state universities, and specialised institutions. Despite the evidence of financial disorder in the 21st century, funding has become a significant issue for the development of public universities (Sheel and Vohra, 2014). Besides, policymakers often design (un)productive schemes; then government approves the budget for such projects for no abundant benefits. For example, a UGC postdoctoral fellowship for 'unemployed' women with doctorates indicates that national citizens are still jobless after holding a doctoral degree. By contrast, it can be inferred that government still supports doctoral graduates even when they are unemployed. The scheme also implies that postdoctoral fellowships are intended not for doctoral graduates interested in them but for those who are unemployed. In a true sense, these fellowships have been funded by the country's taxpayers. One would perceive that policymakers have truly eradicated the purpose of postdoctoral fellowships. Thus, the government should work on productive schemes that benefit all groups of national citizens to establish high-level transparency, especially in higher education.

- **Industry Oriented Research and Innovation**
 - Drawing on the competitiveness of universities in emerging economies, higher education institutions must acquire requisite resources to establish innovation and incubation centres for promoting new ventures and entrepreneurship activities. For instance, it is argued that 'educational institutions train millions of youngsters, but corporates often complain that they do not get the necessary skill and talent required for a job' (Times of India, 2016). To achieve specific goals, institutions must focus on course design, course material, faculty sources, collaborative projects, joint ventures with international universities, and industry sourced and collaborative research centres. These elements not only bridge the gap between academic degrees and industry requirements but also improve the university's overall student activity and performance (see, for example, Schroder et al., 2014 €). Hence, many such initiatives represent the very poor in India due to lack of administrative support and lack of faculty-student engagement. Therefore, universities and companies may design strategic plans to establish research centres to help faculty and students understand the industry needs and requirements.

Partnerships and greater collaboration between the industry and academia will enable the creation of a high-quality higher education ecosystem that keeps pace with the fast-changing demands of jobs. The curriculum must be redesigned and pedagogies continuously improved to allow course correction wherever required. While the scrapping of multiple regulators such as AICTE and UGC and its replacement with HECI is a welcome move, a thorough study of the failures and successes of the previous regulatory mechanism must be undertaken. Moreover, the states must be given fair representation in such a body.

CONCLUSION

To improve the status of higher education, a few productive guidelines are needed for imparting quality academic practices and standards in university education: research funding, collaborative research projects, and a research assessment council. Such initiatives need to be taken up to create a notable impact. The government should embark on schemes to create serious research interest among public and private universities and support the country's economic development. Several universities require training in academic matters such as publishing research, new journal development, research assessment, project funding, and publication houses. In unison, policymakers have to remember that the 'growing trend for accountability within the university system is not limited to research and is mirrored in the assessment of teaching quality, which now feeds into an evaluation of universities to ensure fee-paying students' satisfaction' (Penfield et al., 2014, pp. 22e23).

A digital transformation in higher education, which was already underway, picked up pace due to the COVID-19 pandemic and resultant lockdowns. Online and blended modes of learning may be the way forward. Teaching and learning infrastructure must be developed to adapt to different modes of education. Digital technologies need to be leveraged to address systemic challenges and ensure equity in access and quality. Synchronised digital tools can help offer customised learning solutions according to a student's needs (EY and FICCI, 2021). The government will need to invest in digital infrastructure to bridge the digital divide in the country, which was laid bare during the first phase of the COVID-19 lockdown in India when educational institutions across the country made the switch to digital learning. With this, the government must also develop cyber-resilience and security strategies.

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APPENDIX

TRENDS IN EDUCATION

As of 2015, a total of 8,47,118 primary schools existed in India. The number of upper primary schools was about half the number of primary schools. The number of secondary schools was one-third of the number of upper primary schools. There are only 1,09,318 higher secondary schools in India. A significant decline is observed in the number of schools available, at higher levels of education.

All over India, the enrolment of boys in primary school was higher than that of girls in the academic year 2018-19. The gender gap in enrolment in primary schools was much wider in Haryana, Punjab and Rajasthan. These are also the states with the lowest sex ratios. Meghalaya was the only state which saw gender parity in enrolments at the primary school level.

GENDER-WISE ENROLMENT IN PRIMARY SCHOOLS

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GENDER-WISE ENROLMENT IN ELEMENTARY SCHOOLS

Contrary to enrolment trends in primary and elementary schooling, enrollment at the upper primary level saw girls outnumbering boys in some states. States such as AP, Bihar, Assam, Meghalaya and West Bengal had a higher proportion of girls enrolling in upper primary schools than boys. In Chandigarh, Haryana, Punjab and Rajasthan, the gender gap in enrolments remains skewed in favour of boys.

Assam, Bihar, Chattisgarh, Meghalaya and West Bengal had girls outnumber boys in enrollment at the secondary school level. In enrolments at the secondary school level, Gujrat, Haryana, Punjab, and Rajasthan exhibited a starkly skewed gender gap favouring boys.

Assam, Bihar, Chattisgarh, Meghalaya and West Bengal had girls outnumber boys in enrollment at the secondary school level. In enrolments at the secondary school level, Gujrat, Haryana, Punjab, and Rajasthan exhibited a starkly skewed gender gap favouring boys.

In 2017-18, Haryana, Himachal Pradesh, Punjab and Rajasthan received a boost for Vocational Education under Rashtra Madhyamik Shiksha Abhiyan.

Schools in Telangana, Andhra Pradesh and Madhya Pradesh received extensive coverage under ICT IN 2017-18, as a component of Rashtra Madhyamik Shiksha Abhiyan.

The New Education Policy:

The New Education Policy (NEP) was approved on 29th of July, 2020 by the Union Cabinet, after a gap of 34 years. The previous policy was known as the National Policy on Education (NPE), which was approved in 1986. Later, it got modified in 1992. main focus of NPE was regarding access and equity of education. However, the main focus of NEP is access to quality education. The primary purpose of NEP is to design a vision and framework for school and higher education. The ministry has increased education funding to 6% of GDP, which is now 3% of GDP as per the economic survey 2018-19.

1.1 THE KEY PROPOSALS OF NEW EDUCATIONAL POLICY - 2020:

- The NEP proposes to change the school's academic structure from 10 + 2 years of schooling format to 5+3+3+4 format, where 5 years of foundational course is for 3 to 8 years of age (i.e., class 1 to 2 and 3 years of preschool), 3 years of preparatory years is for 8 to 11 years of age (class 3 to 5), Middle Years of schooling is for class 6 to 8 (i.e., age 11 to 14). The secondary level of schooling is for class 9 to 12 (i.e., age 14 to 18).
- The UG degree structure will be available for 3 and 4 years duration, and it now has multiple entry and exit points.
- Replacing the UGC and AICTE with higher education of India (HECI). HECI will be an umbrella body for entire higher education, excluding medical and legal education. Both Public and private education institutions will be governed by the same set of norms for regulation and academic standards.
- The higher education institution will have the option of offering a one-year master's degree under the new NEP, 2020. So, those who have completed their four years UG degree their Master's will be for one year. The new policy has decided to discontinue the Master in philosophy program.
- Reforming training of teachers: The policy seeks to improve the skills of the teachers by ensuring to institute a large number of merit-based scholarships across the country for studying quality four years integrated Bachelor of Education programs. The teacher will also be offered workshops and online teacher development modules so that they can improve their skills and knowledge.
- Changes to the pattern of examination and the focus on multilingualism in schools: The new education policy will implement standardised school exams to be taken in grades 3, 5, and 8 to track the progress of education throughout the school year rather than just at the end.
- The policy seeks to implement the three-language formula. Still, with flexibility, i.e., without imposing any language on the state, essentially, it means that the students will learn three languages based on state, regions and choice of the student themselves.
- Also, the policy mentions, "the medium of instruction until at least grade 5, but preferably till grade 8 and beyond, will be the home language / mother-tongue / local language" to be followed in both private and private schools.

1.2 KEY PROPOSALS:

Few things which I felt that policy did well in addressing and they are:

1. **Multidisciplinary Undergraduate programs:** This feature will allow the students to explore the world through the lens of multiple subjects; thus, it will provide greater scope and provide holistic and multidisciplinary actions that will help in cross-disciplinary and interdisciplinary thinking.
2. **Entry / Exit:** The flexibility that the NEP will provide for choosing $\frac{3}{4}$ year program, while also allowing some leeway to take gaps within one's bachelor studies. This proposal will enable students to have control over their education and removes the rigid pattern in the current prevalent education system.
3. **Experiential learning:** This proposal would give scope to learn the practical side of the student's choice of subject, which would further open the scope to improve their employability.
4. **Teacher-student ratio (30:1 / 25:1):** Maintaining teacher-student ratio will open room for more interactive sessions in the class, and also, a teacher can keep a tab on the maximum no of students. The areas having a large number of socio-economically disadvantaged students will aim for a ratio of 25:1.
5. **Learning how to learn:** This is a phrase that means the ability to organise one's learning through effective management of time and information. Thus, experiential learning, interdisciplinary and multidisciplinary programs will help to learn and apply in the real world.
6. **Breakfast along with the midday meal:** will provide the students from socio-economically disadvantaged backgrounds to concentrate on studies and also will give an assurance to their parents about the child's health. This might help in an increase in the enrolment ratio.

FEATURES OF THE NEW EDUCATION POLICY

1.3 RESERVATIONS ABOUT THE NEW EDUCATION POLICY:

1. Free education stances replaced by affordability: The document talks about accessibility and affordable cost for providing education to all across the country, including socio-economically disadvantaged groups and for those living in rural and remote areas. Nowhere does it talk about free education.
2. Trained volunteers from both the local communities and beyond, social workers, counsellors and community involvement: Firstly, I am quite sceptical about the sentence “trained volunteers from the local communities and beyond. It doesn’t mention the kind of training they would be provided. So, many questions remain unanswered:
 - Who are the trained volunteers from the local communities and beyond?
 - What is the qualification required to become one?
 - What is the age limit of these volunteers, and so on?

3. No commitment to replace contract and ad-hoc teachers with dignified service conditions: Although it talks about teachers' training and skill development, yet it has no provision for replacing contract and ad-hoc teachers.
4. No space for a reservation: Reservation is meant to ensure representation of those castes which have been discriminated in the name of caste for years. Reservation in the school/ workplace provides equity among the people, which takes a back seat in the New Education policy.
5. Privatisation of Education: This would only accelerate the commodification of education and will create a situation where higher studies will become a privilege only for those who can afford it, which would be a question of equity principle for the people who come from a marginalised background.

RESERVATIONS ABOUT THE NEW EDUCATION POLICY

CONCLUSION

To conclude, I would say that it's quite extraordinary and a bold move by the government to bring in transformation and restructure the education system with the radical changes. However, it fails to take into consideration the disadvantageous (socio-economically background) to access education because of the following reasons:

1. Multiple entry and exit might create an immense disparity between financially able and disabled students as financially able students will get a higher chance for studies and will be able to acquire better opportunities.
2. Under NEP, the private and self-governing college will receive more autonomy, and this will create a situation where higher education will become a privilege only for those who can afford it. Hence, it will only accelerate the commodification of education.
3. Next is that the English language used to give India an edge for many opportunities. However, discontinuing English as a medium might be disadvantageous for lower caste populations as they see English as a way to escape the caste hierarchy.

However, only the method of implementation will determine its success and failure.

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